

1 **Time-resolved probing of laser-induced nanostructuring processes in** 2 **liquids**

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15 **Abstract**

16 Laser synthesis and processing of colloids (LSPC) in liquids has gained widespread applications
17 in producing nanomaterials of different classes of solids. While the technical processes in differ-
18 ent cases of ablation, fragmentation or colloid fusing may look macroscopically different in each
19 application the underlying fundamental mechanisms are always the same cascade of laser interac-
20 tion with matter, non-thermal or thermal energy deposition, phase transitions and the subsequent
21 structure formation processes. Disentangling these mechanisms represents a veritable challenge,
22 as ultrafast and structurally sensitive experimental methods are required. This review presents a
23 discussion of how state-of-the-art experimental protocols using ultrafast lasers and sensitive struc-
24 tural probes, such as electrons or x-rays are able to address this cascade. In particular, it is possible
25 to investigate LSPC on single objects, using single probe pulses and avoid accumulation effects in
26 a heterogeneous sample. The presented results capture structure formation with femtosecond and
27 atomic scale resolution.

28 **Keywords**

29 laser processing in liquids, time-resolved probing, single objects, x-ray scattering, optical imaging,
30 optical spectroscopy, electron diffraction, pump-probe

List of used abbreviations

CB	cavitation bubble
CDI	coherent diffraction imaging
fs, ps, ns, μ s	femto-, pico-, nano-, microsecond
IR	infrared
LAA	laser ablation in air
LAL	laser ablation in liquid
LFL	laser fragmentation in liquid
LML	laser melting in liquid
LSPC	laser synthesis and processing of colloids
MD	Molecular dynamics
MeV-UED	mega-electron-volt ultrafast electron diffraction
31 NP	nanoparticle
PPE	Pump-probe ellipsometry
PPM	pump-probe microscopy
PPI	pump-probe interferometry
PPS	pump-probe shadowgraphy
SAXS	small-angle x-ray scattering
SPR	surface plasmon resonance
TAS	transient absorption spectroscopy
TTM	two-temperature model
TTM-MD	two-temperature model molecular dynamics
UED	ultrafast electron diffraction
WAXS	wide-angle x-ray scattering
XFEL	X-ray Free Electron Laser

32 Introduction

33 Laser synthesis and processing of materials (LSPC) with emphasis on structure formation on the
34 nanoscale offers a multitude of pathways to desired structure-related function [1]. In green pro-
35 cesses, nanostructures and nanoparticles (NPs) can be produced that serve applications in many
36 fields, such as heterogeneous catalysis [2,3], (bio)photonics [4] and coating or device fabrication
37 [5]. In a bottom-up approach the products of the laser-based synthesis are not defined by direct
38 spatial control, but by harnessing the energetic and structural relaxation pathways of fundamen-
39 tal reactions that span from atomic to macroscopic length scales. Consequently, it is paramount to
40 understand the complex cascades that follow laser irradiation of condensed matter. Of particular
41 importance here is the processing in the presence of liquids surrounding the irradiated material, but
42 also exchanging energy and material with the excited loci.

43 LSPC commonly encompasses laser ablation in liquid (LAL), which allows producing NPs from
44 a surface of virtually any solid [6-9], laser fragmentation in liquid (LFL) to further reduce dimen-
45 sions of particles down to few-atom clusters [10-13], or laser fusion, resp. laser melting in liquid

46 (LML) [14,15]. The latter is used to achieve the opposite effect of increasing particle size with the
47 aim for high quality in shape or size.

48 The presence of a liquid in laser processing on the one hand has practical advantages, such as sim-
49 ple handling and safe suspension of the products for further use. On the other hand, the interaction
50 of the irradiated surfaces and NPs with the liquid forms an active interface for energy exchange,
51 leading to extreme cooling rates of 1000 K per nanosecond, which quenches melted particles, gen-
52 erates ablation and fragmentation products with a high defect density, and enhances catalytic ac-
53 tivity. In addition, the liquid may also participate in the reaction by electrostatic stabilization [12],
54 formation of gases [16], or chemical interaction with the target to enhance redox reactions or passi-
55 vating coatings [17-19].

56 The understanding of LSPC in liquids has been largely stimulated by theoretical approaches and
57 simulations. In a thermodynamic approach the equilibration of excited electrons with the phonon
58 bath is described in the two-temperature model (TTM) [20-22], which conveys important conse-
59 quences, such as providing time scales for lattice heating or explaining nonnonlinearities in ex-
60 citation through electron heat capacity [23]. One notable exception from the universality of the
61 TTM that limits its generalization to more degrees of freedom is the impact of non-thermalized
62 electrons on structure formation via direct and near-field forces [24-27]. Furthermore, the appli-
63 cation of TTM is hampered by the relatively high uncertainty of material parameters such as the
64 temperature- or field-dependent interaction cross section or the non-linear heat capacities [28-31].
65 Heat flow and phase transitions can be well modeled by classical approaches down to nanometer
66 scales in a local thermodynamic equilibrium [32-34]. A synthesis of the different coevolving phe-
67 nomena with excitation and dissipation requires more detailed numerical approaches [35] or simu-
68 lations. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations [36,37] are widely used to predict phase transitions
69 or structure formation on the nanoscale [38,39], but ultimately also require interfacing the simula-
70 tions with other models, such as TTM [40,41] or large-scale hydrodynamics [42-45]. This integra-
71 tion approach leads to computationally demanding studies that eventually show convergence with
72 experimental results.

73 Generally, the classification of the mechanisms in LSPC identifies three main pathways that are
74 pictured schematically in Fig. 1: (i) thermal processes, where the condensed matter is heated to
75 high lattice temperatures, leading to melting, reshaping (Fig. 1 B, C), evaporation and phase ex-
76 plosion near the critical point (Fig. 1 H)[39,46-48]; (ii) stress-induced decompositions, where
77 competition between heating and expansion leads to spallation or cavitation [36,49,50] (Fig. 1 D);
78 (iii) non-thermal processes, where excessive electron emission leads to material decomposition via
79 charge forces [51,52] (Fig. 1 D, E, F, G). Discriminating between these mechanisms in experiments
80 is challenging and requires carefully designed approaches that resolve the processes spatially, tem-
81 porally, and energetically.

82 This review introduces specific questions and results pertaining to the understanding of laser ma-
83 terial processing relevant to NP synthesis and manipulation. Since a manifold of individual mech-
84 anistic processes can be initiated by intense pulsed laser excitation, it is challenging to disentangle
85 the structural relaxations crossing all the time and length scales, as well as to discriminate individ-
86 ual structural pathways from an average sampling over repetitive pulses, varying fluence or ensem-

87 ble of nonidentical NPs and structures. While optical methods have been paramount to understand-
 88 ing structural processes and verifying proposed pathways, we describe spatially and temporally
 89 resolved optical reflectivity and short-wavelength scattering methods that are able to directly re-
 90 veal structural motifs. Ultimately, it is possible to investigate single NPs with a single shot before
 91 complete destruction. With these methods, we describe structural pathways for particle generation,
 92 fragmentation, and energy coupling to the liquid environment to establish a mechanistic knowledge
 93 of fundamental and applied processes.

Figure 1: Scheme of fundamental structural relaxations of laser-excited metal NPs in liquid environment. (A) After short-pulse excitation the laser field imposes anisotropic forces due to the surface plasmon resonance (SPR), which can lead to a Coulomb instability with spallation or near-field ablation. Particles melt after high intensity excitation, which is accompanied by bubble formation in the liquid after heat dissipation. Possible channels for fragmentation include strain-induced explosion as well as thermal phase explosion. (B-E) Several stages of morphology changes of excited gold particles after single-pulse irradiation at 20, 50, 100 and 200 J/m² (from left). (F) Photon-induced near-field imaging of the SPR of gold particles in a silica shell in an electron microscope together with the directional fission due to the directed charge emission (G). (H) results of numerical simulations of femtosecond particle excitation (15 nm) at 1000 J/m² in a delay sequence from 46 to 281 ps (from left); (I) numerical simulation of femtosecond particle excitation (20 nm) at an absorbed fluence of 84 J/m² in a delay sequence up to 50 ps. Figures 1 B-E were adapted with permission from [51], Copyright 2011 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figures 1 F and G were reprinted with permission from [52], Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Fig. 1 H was adapted with permission from [39], Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 1 I was reproduced from [53] (© 2024 J. Hwang et al., some rights reserved; exclusive licensee American Association for the Advancement of Science, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. .

94 The first chapter entitled “Ultrafast light-matter interaction directly observed via single-pulse

95 single-particle imaging” describes the processes initiated by laser-excitation of an individual NP
96 probed by X-ray scattering up to delay times of a few tens of picoseconds. The second chapter
97 “Structural dynamics in liquids” reports on the application of ultrafast time-resolved electron scat-
98 tering to investigate early-time structural relaxation and chemical bond dynamics in laser-induced
99 ionization of liquid water. In the third chapter “Nanoparticle excitation in an ensemble and energy
100 exchange with medium”, an approach is shown on how reactions of both the excited NPs as well as
101 the interaction with the surrounding liquid can be resolved in one experiment. And finally, a fourth
102 chapter provides a state-of-the-art overview on the subject “Large-scale optical probing of laser
103 ablation dynamics in liquids”. Here, the relaxation dynamics of a few tens of micron sized laser-
104 excited surface, as used in many setups designed for NP generation by laser ablation in liquid, is
105 probed with optical methods from the picosecond time domain up to the final state in the millisec-
106 ond domain.

107 **Ultrafast light-matter interaction directly observed via single-pulse** 108 **single-particle imaging**

109 The interaction of intense laser fields with matter has significantly enriched our understanding
110 of material deformation and phase transition kinetics, drawing increasing attention to strongly
111 driven physical systems[54]. Hidden material phases revealed under non-equilibrium conditions
112 have expanded research on photoinduced ultrafast phenomena, enabling precise control of mate-
113 rial properties [55-58]. This advancement has catalyzed new directions in nanomaterial process-
114 ing and synthesis, such as producing controlled NPs through ultrafast laser-matter interactions. A
115 notable example is the production of monodisperse NPs in aqueous solutions via laser pulse ex-
116 posures [1,59], demonstrating practical applications and underscoring the need for deeper insights
117 into non-equilibrium light-matter interactions.

118 Experimental approaches to uncover the underlying reaction kinetics of such complex interactions
119 have been diverse and continuously evolving [26,60-64]. X-ray or electron diffraction techniques
120 (Fig.2), implemented via pump-probe schemes and combined with femtosecond ultrashort pulses,
121 have enabled the observation of ultrafast atomic-scale motions [65]. During these transitions, tran-
122 sient and previously unknown material phases emerge, highlighting the existence of states accessi-
123 ble only under strongly driven non-equilibrium conditions. This insight has spurred further investi-
124 gations into ultrafast reaction kinetics beyond the thermodynamic limit. However, these diffraction
125 techniques often yield ensemble-averaged dynamics with Ångstrom-scale spatial resolution, as they
126 rely on well-resolved interference fringes from periodic crystalline structures. Consequently, local
127 structural variations are frequently obscured and data interpretation is constrained by predefined
128 models. These limitations become even more pronounced when studying non-equilibrium states,
129 such as laser-induced material deformation kinetics, where established knowledge is still develop-
130 ing.

131 To address these challenges, direct imaging probes with high spatial and temporal resolution have
132 been developed [66-68]. Direct imaging offers the advantage of studying non-equilibrium phase
133 transitions without relying on *a priori* models.

Figure 2: Time resolved experiments using ultrashort X-ray or electron pulses via a pump-probe method. (A) Time resolved X-ray diffraction investigates the ultrafast dynamics of various long range orders in crystals. (B) Lab-based four-dimensional transmission electron microscope for direct imaging of single specimens or crystalline lattices. (C) Ultrafast holographic X-ray imaging investigation relaxation systems. (D) Single particle dynamics imaging with single XFEL pulses in directly imaging the irreversible kinetics, Figure 2 A is from [69] (©2023 H. Lee et al., published by IUCr Journals, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License). Figure 2 B is reprinted from [70]. Copyright (2005) of National Academy of Sciences, U.S.A. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 2C was reprinted with permission from [64] C. von Korff-Schmising et al., Phys. Rev. Lett. 112, p. 217203 (2014), Copyright (2014) by the American Physical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 2 D was reprinted from [68] (© 2024 Y. Ihm et al., published by Springer Nature, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

134 In pump-probe imaging experiments, specimens are excited using femtosecond optical laser pulses
135 and subsequently imaged at defined time delays to capture their dynamic responses. This method is
136 particularly advantageous for visualizing structural changes in single particles. Although technical
137 challenges remain in achieving sufficient signal-to-noise ratios, single-particle imaging uniquely
138 resolves local fluctuations that are otherwise averaged out in ensemble measurements. Recogniz-
139 ing that structural inhomogeneities drive emergent material properties, the ability to observe such
140 local fluctuations is increasingly vital. Single-particle imaging with several nm spatial and several
141 tens of ns temporal resolution has been demonstrated using electron microscopy [71]. By integrat-
142 ing a photocathode-based ultrashort electron pulse generator into a lab-based electron microscope,
143 dynamic imaging of single specimens via pump-probe electron microscopy became possible. For
144 instance, a spin state transition in metal-organic framework Fe(pyrazine)Pt(CN)₄ NPs was induced
145 by nanosecond laser pulses, resulting in a high- to low-spin transition accompanied by morphologi-
146 cal deformations coupled with lattice dynamics.

147 Femtosecond X-ray laser pulses from X-ray free-electron lasers (XFELs) have further revolution-
148 ized dynamic X-ray imaging. Coherent diffraction imaging (CDI) [66,68,72,73], utilizes the spatial
149 coherence of X-ray laser pulses such that the fully coherent diffraction pattern of an object is re-
150 constructed by iterative phase retrieval algorithms retrieving the object density. This technique is
151 particularly suited for time-resolved imaging of dynamic processes, which show transient states
152 that exist only for femtoseconds. While the initial demonstration used the forward scattered inten-
153 sity (small-angle x-ray scattering, SAXS) to derive the spatial scattering length distribution (related
154 to material density) an extension allowed reconstructing scattering at Bragg peaks (in wide-angle
155 x-ray scattering (WAXS) geometry) to specifically reconstruct the distribution of crystallinity and
156 lattice strain [74]. In pump-probe configuration photo-induced strain field oscillations in single Au
157 nanocrystals [75] have been resolved. These studies revealed large-scale NP deformations caused
158 by thermally excited elastic strains. However, stroboscopic measurements like these are limited
159 to systems that recover their original states after perturbation and are unsuitable for studying irre-
160 versible kinetic reactions in strongly driven non-equilibrium phenomena.

161 The development of single-pulse, single-particle imaging using XFELs has enabled nanoscale res-
162 olution observations of ultrafast irreversible processes. XFELs' unique combination of spatial co-
163 herence, ultrafast brightness, and femtosecond pulse durations provides a powerful probe for study-
164 ing strong light-field and matter interactions. Investigations into photo-induced melting, a long-
165 standing yet incompletely understood phenomenon, have highlighted the role of non-thermal pro-
166 cesses [29,76-78]. For example, time-resolved resonant X-ray scattering studies have directly ob-
167 served ultrafast reconfiguration of bonding orbitals in Ge crystals, revealing a coexistence of ther-
168 mal and non-thermal melting mechanisms [69,79]. Local regions breaking translational symmetry
169 and initiating the melting of the entire specimen were revealed through single-pulse, single-particle
170 imaging, providing a microscopic understanding of the melting transition [68].

171 The single-particle dynamic CDI discussed here can be compared with the aforementioned Bragg
172 CDI, highlighting their distinct technical advantages for addressing specific scientific challenges.
173 Bragg-CDI measures coherent diffuse scattering patterns around a specific Bragg reflection of a
174 specimen. A full three-dimensional mapping of the coherent scattering pattern along a particular

175 Bragg reflection is achieved by rocking the specimen while maintaining the Bragg reflection con-
176 dition. The oversampled coherent 3D diffraction pattern obtained is then phase-retrieved to image
177 the specimen, revealing strained lattice deformations along the direction parallel to the Bragg re-
178 flection. Whilst this Bragg-CDI offers exceptional sensitivity to lattice strain fields formed over the
179 whole specimen, its imaging capability relies on successfully collecting a complete 3D map of the
180 diffuse pattern surrounding a specific Bragg reflection. This method requires initial alignment of
181 the specimen to a Bragg reflection and repeated restorations to its original, intact state during the
182 collection of the entire 3D map via crystal rocking. Consequently, it is not well-suited for study-
183 ing nonequilibrium kinetics such as strong light-matter interactions that involve irreversible phase
184 changes.

185 In contrast, the single-particle single-pulse CDI introduced here overcomes such limitations. Each
186 single-pulse coherent diffraction pattern is acquired in transmission geometry using a single X-ray
187 pulse, eliminating the need for specimen alignment to a specific Bragg angle. This ensures that the
188 specimen can be completely damaged after a single pulse measurement, as fresh specimens can be
189 used for subsequent single-pulse exposures. The only requirement is that all specimens must be
190 structurally (morphologically) identical to the extent dictated by the image resolution. This condi-
191 tion is practically achievable due to remarkable advancements in monodisperse NP synthesis. Each
192 single-pulse coherent diffraction pattern is collected from a new, fresh specimen with completely
193 independent experimental parameters. Time-resolved imaging is accomplished by controlling the
194 delay time between the pump and probe pulses. The reliability of experimental data is ensured by
195 collecting multiple datasets for a given delay time, thereby avoiding misinterpretations of reaction
196 kinetics caused by fluctuations in individual single-particle images.

197 Here, single Au nanospheres were irradiated with femtosecond infrared (fs-IR) laser pulses, rapidly
198 increasing the electron temperature to several tens of thousands of Kelvin within a few hundred
199 femtoseconds. Photoexcited hot electrons in metallic Au transferred their excess kinetic energy by
200 colliding with other conduction electrons and Au ions, which subsequently increased the lattice
201 temperature, reaching equilibrium within a few tens of picoseconds.

202 Interestingly, ultrafast single-particle imaging revealed unexpected phenomena that deviate from
203 conventional TTM that describes energy transfer between electrons and the lattice. Although the
204 dynamics of photoexcited hot electrons were expected to uniformly affect the entire specimen
205 within a few picoseconds, the experiment instead observed inhomogeneous and laser-polarization-
206 dependent anisotropic melting. This indicates that residual effects from the initial electron dynam-
207 ics play a dominant role in influencing ionic dynamics at later stages, persisting for several to tens
208 of picoseconds.

209 Localized surface plasmon formations in metallic NPs, followed by their annihilation, have been
210 identified as key contributors to the observed anisotropic melting behavior. These findings, corrob-
211 orated by MD simulations that incorporate the TTM (TTM-MD), suggest that energy accumulation
212 in localized hotspots drives anisotropic melting. Nevertheless, direct experimental evidence linking
213 electronic and ionic dynamics across multiscale time domains remains elusive.

214 Multiplexing probes, such as the combination of imaging and crystal diffraction, have advanced
215 the understanding of complex phenomena by narrowing the gap between theory and observa-

Figure 3: Single particle investigation via multiplexing experiments. (A) XFEL single-pulse multiplexing experiment is shown. By implementing a wide-angle detector close to the interaction spot, the crystal structure is monitored in addition to the sample densities in the projection images. (B) TTM-MD by corroborating the atomic structure information and heterogeneous sample morphology describes the melting process in atomic scale. (C) Overall photo-induced melting process of single Au NP is depicted. Figure 3 was adapted with permission from [80], Copyright 2023 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

216 tion (Fig.3) [80,81]. In an experiment combining single-particle imaging with wide-angle crystal
 217 diffraction, additional detectors near the specimen captured crystal Bragg reflections, offering new
 218 insights into photoinduced melting. The study revealed that local atomic disorder begins at the sur-
 219 face before the overall lattice expands, with the melt front progressing from the particle surface
 220 and grain boundaries, as evidenced by a reduction in crystal domain sizes. Direct imaging of void
 221 formation further deepened the understanding of the process, showing that voids act as primary
 222 drivers of the transition, corroborated by TTM-MD simulations and additional single-particle ex-
 223 periments. These voids form due to local pressure differences caused by energy accumulation in
 224 hot spots via photoexcited localized surface plasmons, with the overall melting and particle dis-
 225 integration resembling an inverted crystal nucleation process, where voids act as seeds and their
 226 expansion mirrors crystal growth [53].

227 While a fundamental understanding of phase transitions driven by ultrafast and intense laser fields
 228 is emerging, many details remain elusive. A key unresolved issue is how femtosecond-scale pho-
 229 toinduced electron dynamics can drive much slower ionic motion with several orders of magnitude
 230 timing lag, a phenomenon that demands paradigm-shifting insights supported by direct experimen-
 231 tal evidence, unconstrained by traditional equilibrium thermodynamics. Alongside the ongoing
 232 effort to understand ultrafast laser-matter interactions, focused research on manipulating phase-
 233 transition kinetics using femtosecond laser pulses is critical. Such research promises to improve the
 234 ability to engineer functional materials through on-demand customization.

235 Recognizing that photoexcited electrons serve as the initial point, it is intuitive to envision control-
 236 ling localized surface plasmons through the wavelength and polarization state of femtosecond laser
 237 pulses [82]. Active research in this domain is anticipated to facilitate the precise optical control of
 238 material phases. Furthermore, advances in imaging technologies, particularly those enabling ul-
 239 trafast, three-dimensional, and atomic-scale time-resolved imaging, will be pivotal in elucidating

240 local atomic-scale structural dynamics directly associated with photoinduced electron behavior.
241 The introduction of MHz repetition-rate XFELs is expected to significantly propel these endeavors.
242 This will coincide with the substantial production of single-pulse data, which awaits prompt online
243 analysis to facilitate practical implementation of the investigation. Such streamlined management
244 of large data sets can be supported by implementing machine learning algorithms. We anticipate a
245 more pronounced utilization of deep learning initially in massive data analysis and also in extract-
246 ing concealed signals to complete high-resolution 3D imaging [83]. Additionally, adapting single-
247 pulse XFEL time-resolved imaging to ultrafast electron sources may provide even higher spatial
248 and temporal resolution, further enhancing our comprehension of these intricate processes. The
249 development of new large-scale facilities is actively underway through international collaboration.
250 This progress will significantly enhance accessibility for researchers from diverse fields, extending
251 beyond X-ray or electron scattering, and provide a versatile experimental platform to explore strong
252 light-matter interactions.

253 **Structural dynamics in liquids**

254 For laser-based materials processing in liquids, including techniques of LAL, LFL and LML, a key
255 challenge lies in managing the intricate interplay between laser energy deposition, plasma genera-
256 tion, and the dynamic behavior of the surrounding liquid environment. The liquid medium not only
257 mediates energy transfer but also plays a crucial role in influencing NP generation mechanisms,
258 shock wave propagation, and bubble dynamics. Understanding the liquid dynamics is therefore es-
259 sential for optimizing process parameters, improving reproducibility, and tailoring material proper-
260 ties for specific applications. Ultrafast optical techniques such as transient absorption spectroscopy
261 (TAS)[84-87] have been applied to investigate the influence of the liquid environment on the en-
262 ergy relaxation processes of laser-excited NPs. While the TAS technique provides insight into the
263 electronic properties of the NPs, it is, however, unable to reveal the response of the surrounding
264 liquid to the excitation. To this end, the time-resolved scattering techniques based on X-rays and
265 electrons are more appropriate because of their capability of visualizing atomic-scale structure evo-
266 lution.

267 In this section, we focus on the time-resolved electron scattering technique, also known as ultrafast
268 electron diffraction (UED). We review the fundamental principles of this technique and present an
269 example of its application in studying structural dynamics in ionized liquid water.

270 Electrons and X-rays can both be used to structurally characterize the sample material and are often
271 combined to best understand a sample. Electrons are sensitive to the electrostatic potential of the
272 object, and hence can probe both electrons and nuclei, whereas X-rays predominantly interact with
273 the electron ingredient of the object. Furthermore, for samples such as liquid water, electron scat-
274 tering probes both O-O and O-H intermolecular bonds, while X-ray scattering is specifically sen-
275 sitive to the O-O bond distance [89]. However, time-resolved liquid scattering studies with the use
276 of electrons have been hindered by their shallow penetration depth ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$) compared to that of
277 hard X-rays ($> 100 \mu\text{m}$). Recently, the development of free-flowing liquid sheet jet has overcome
278 this limitation by providing flat liquid sheets with thickness down to tens of nanometers [90,91].

279 The integration of this capability with a mega-electron-volt UED (MeV-UED) system has enabled
 280 electron scattering experiments for a variety of liquid-phase systems [88,89,92-94].
 281 Figure 4A presents the schematic diagram of the liquid electron scattering experiments conducted
 282 at the MeV-UED facility of SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory. This setup featured a high
 283 brightness, femtosecond electron beam operating at 3–4 MeV energies, coupled with a rapid-flow
 284 liquid sheet jet system that ensures the sample was refreshed before each pump-probe shot se-
 285 quence. The scattering electrons of the liquid sample pumped by a synchronized femtosecond laser
 286 pulse were then recorded by a detector as a scattering pattern which provided a momentum transfer
 287 range (denoted by q) reaching as large as 10 \AA^{-1} , c.f. Fig. 4B for the liquid water scattering pat-
 288 tern. Here $q = 4\pi \sin \theta / \lambda$, where θ is the scattering angle, and λ is the de Broglie wavelength of
 289 the electrons. Figure 4C shows the raw scattering intensity lineout of liquid water that was obtained
 290 by azimuthal averaging the scattering pattern. The raw scattering intensity lineout includes contri-
 291 butions from elastic scattering, inelastic scattering and system-specific background. With the last
 292 two components removed, the total elastic scattering signal (Fig. 4D) exhibits a distribution typical
 293 of amorphous materials with two major humps situated between 1 and 4 \AA^{-1} , consistent with the
 294 X-ray scattering measurement as shown in Fig. 9.

295 The total elastic scattering, $I(q)$, can be expressed as the sum of atomic, $I_{at}(q)$, and molecular,
 296 $I_{mol}(q)$, scattering terms: $I(q) = I_{at}(q) + I_{mol}(q)$. The contribution of the atomic scattering to the
 297 overall scattering intensity is given by the sum of all the elastic scattering amplitudes for all atoms
 298 in the system:

$$299 \quad I_{at}(q) = \sum_{i=1}^N |f_i(q)|^2, \quad (1)$$

300 where N is the number of atoms in the system and $f_i(q)$ is the elastic scattering amplitude, also
 301 known as atomic scattering factor, for the i -th atom. As indicated by the above equation, the atomic
 302 scattering contribution does not contain any structural information, and its intensity depends only
 303 on the atoms present in the molecule. It is worth noting that the atomic scattering factor for elec-
 304 trons can be calculated via a Fourier transform of the atomic potential, while for X-rays it can be
 305 obtained using a Fourier transform of electron density. The two results are however interchangeable
 306 using the Mott-Bethe formula [95] given by :

$$307 \quad f_i^{Electron}(q) = \frac{1}{8\pi^2 a_0} \frac{Z_i - f_i^{X-ray}(q)}{q^2}, \quad (2)$$

308 where a_0 is the Bohr radius, and Z_i is the atomic number of the i -th atom.

309 The molecular scattering contribution is given by the sum of interference terms for all atom pairs in
 310 the system:

$$311 \quad I_{mol}(q) = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j \neq 1}^N |f_i(q)| |f_j(q)| \cos(\eta_i - \eta_j) \frac{\sin(qr_{ij})}{qr_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

312 where $f_i(q)$ and $f_j(q)$ are the elastic scattering amplitudes of the i-th and j-th atom, respectively,
 313 and η_i and η_j are their corresponding phases; r_{ij} is the internuclear separation between the i-th and
 314 j-th atoms. The interference term of the molecular scattering gives rise to the modulation feature
 315 of the total elastic scattering intensity, while the atomic scattering forms a global baseline that de-
 316 cays exponentially with q . This is still true for unoriented molecules in liquids, which do not need
 317 to show long-range positional correlations, but only intramolecular fixed bond distances and inter-
 318 molecular short-range correlation, which can be captured by the statistical pair distribution func-
 319 tion.

320 In pump-probe experiments, the optical excitation results in molecular structural changes, thus the
 321 differential scattering signal with respect to the unpumped signal solely contains the molecular
 322 structural information, i.e.: $\Delta I(q, t) = I(q, t) - I(q, t < 0) = \Delta I_{mol}(q, t)$. The molecular structural
 323 change can be retrieved through a differential pair distribution function (ΔPDF) given by:

$$324 \quad \Delta PDF(r, t) = \int_{q_{min}}^{q_{max}} \Delta sM(q, t) \exp(-kq^2) \sin(qr) dq, \quad (4)$$

325 where $\Delta sM(q, t) = q \frac{\Delta I_{mol}(q, t)}{I_{ar}(q)}$, and $\exp(-kq^2)$ with k a constant is a damping function to suppress
 326 high frequency artifacts generated by the truncation of $\Delta sM(q, t)$ at q_{min} and q_{max} . What ΔPDF
 327 essentially reflects is the local structural change between the excited state and the ground state at
 328 different interatomic distances of the molecule. Positive peaks in ΔPDF indicate an increased prob-
 329 ability of finding atom pairs at specific distances, while negative peaks reflect a decreased probab-
 330 ility.

331 Here, we showcase the work done by Lin *et al.* [94] investigating the early-time structural dynam-
 332 ics in radiolysis of liquid water using the technique of time-resolved electron scattering (Figure
 333 5). As context, the elementary reaction pathways in ionized water have been extensively studied
 334 [96]. Upon ionization, liquid water produces hydrated electrons and water cations (H_2O^+), which
 335 undergo proton transfer with neighboring water molecules at time scales shorter than 100 fs to gen-
 336 erate hydroxyl radicals (OH) and hydronium cations (H_3O^+) [97]. Simultaneously, the ionized elec-
 337 trons in the excited p-like state undergo rapid solvation by neighboring water molecules in ~ 50 fs
 338 or transitions nonadiabatically to the s-like state at a similar time scale [98-100]. The hydrated and
 339 thermalized electrons then recombine with ion cores and hydroxyl radicals through geminate and
 340 non-geminate recombination processes, evolving on timescales ranging from tens of picoseconds to
 341 nanoseconds [100].

342 In this work, Lin *et al.* investigated the transient intermediate complex formed along the reaction
 343 pathways of ionized water and the corresponding structural dynamics following the proton transfer
 344 reaction. Time-resolved electron scattering proved to be an ideal technique for this study, since
 345 it provided sufficiently large momentum transfer and femtosecond temporal resolution required
 346 to capture the change in the bond distance of an ultrafast chemical reaction. These results would
 347 certainly contribute to the understanding of the liquid dynamics in laser excitation of solvated NPs,

348 especially regarding the ionization and heating of the liquid water environment either directly by
349 the laser electric field under high-intensity regime or through electron ejections from the NPs.
350 Figure 5 (A) - (C) show the result of $\Delta I_{mol}(q, t)$ for the first 2 ps after laser excitation, with corre-
351 sponding Δ PDF result presented in Figure 5 (D) - (F). After laser excitation, Δ PDF clearly shows
352 pair density reductions at radial distances corresponding to O \cdots H hydrogen bond and the first three
353 O \cdots O coordination shells of neutral water. For better illustration, these atom pairs are highlighted
354 in a virtual liquid water system as shown in Fig. 5 (G). Another key feature with Δ PDF result is the
355 appearance of new atomic-pair distances in between O \cdots H and O \cdots O bonds.
356 Equally interesting is the rapid change of these signals in the time domain, the underlying physical
357 picture of which is provided in Fig. 5 (H). Nonetheless, the transient structure averaged over the
358 first 200 fs showed that two correlation peaks were formed at 1.4 and 2.4 Å, respectively, as shown
359 in Fig. 5 (E). These two peaks were attributed to the O \cdots H and O \cdots O bond distances of the sol-
360 vated OH(H₃O⁺) pair before separation. The experimental result showed that these features were
361 short-lived and disappeared within \sim 250 fs. This separation occurred because of the subsequent
362 proton propagation from H₃O⁺ to the outer shell neutral water. The radical-cation pair dissociation
363 process coincided with the heating of the water and contributed to the growth of signals at 3.4 and
364 5.8 Å at a later time. The overall change of the signal was observed to be steady after 500 fs. Inter-
365 estingly, the experimental Δ PDF at a steady state could be well described by the temperature jump
366 effect ($\Delta T \sim 320$ K) of neutral water, as shown by the agreement with the MD simulation result in
367 Fig. 5 (F). This implied that the rearrangement of the water molecular structure was dominated by
368 the heating effect when the steady state was reached. These observations and the approach of an-
369 alyzing the water structure provide an alternative pathway to understanding the energy dissipation
370 pertinent to NP excitation in a liquid medium, as described in the next section.

371 The above-mentioned results highlight the capability of UED technique in probing laser-induced
372 structural dynamics in liquid-phase systems. In particular, its femtosecond time resolution and
373 ability to access large momentum transfer enable real-time imaging of chemical bond dynamics.
374 We anticipate that UED will complement X-ray scattering techniques in studying liquid dynamics,
375 providing critical insights into energy dissipation processes in laser-excited NPs within a liquid en-
376 vironment. Potential applications of UED include investigating the non-thermal heating of water
377 molecules surrounding NPs, which occurs on femtosecond to picosecond timescales, as well as ex-
378 amining the response of the water environment to heat transfer and the mechanical work performed
379 by the expanding NPs.

Figure 4: MeV-UED studies of structure dynamics in solution. (A) Schematic diagram of the experimental setup. An ultrathin liquid sheet was pumped by the fs optical pulse, and probed by a synchronized MeV electron beam. The scattering electrons were recorded as a scattering pattern at the detector. (B) An example of the electron scattering pattern for liquid water. (C) Azimuthally averaged scattering signal for liquid water at 290 K. (D) UED, X-ray and simulated elastic scattering curves of liquid water. Figures 4 A-D were adapted from [88] (© 2020 J. P. F. Nunes et al., published by AIP Publishing, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

Figure 5: MeV-UED studies of ionized liquid water. (A) Experimental results of $\Delta I_{mol}(q, t)$. (B) Reconstructed $\Delta I_{mol}(q, t)$ from 2D global fit. (C) Evolution associated spectra (EAS) from the global fit under the assumption of first-order kinetics (EAS1 \rightarrow EAS2). (D) $\Delta PDF(r, t)$ results of the ionized liquid water. (E) and (F) Selected experimental transient diffraction signals at averaged delay from 0 to 0.2 ps (E) and at 1.85 ps (F). The pink trace in (F) represents the ΔPDF between hot water at 610 K and water at 290 K from MD simulations. (G) Graphic representation of atom pairs in liquid water. (H) Cartoons showing the ionization of liquid water and formation of solvated hydronium, hydroxyl radical, and electron, followed by the local thermalization through nonradiative relaxation. Figures 5 A-F and H are from [94]. Reprinted with permission from AAAS. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 5 G is reprinted with permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry, from [89] (“Structure retrieval in liquid-phase electron scattering” by J. Yang et al., Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys., vol. 23, issue 2, © 2021); permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

380 Nanoparticle excitation in an ensemble and energy exchange with 381 medium

382 With the latest advances in ultrafast imaging down to an atomic scale (see section of single-particle
383 imaging) it became possible to visualize photo-reactions in individual particles [68,101,102], in-
384 cluding internal strain distribution or polar vortices [103]. In addition to focusing on single, se-
385 lected particles it is also possible to perform such experiments as massively repeated single-shot
386 imaging to cover heterogeneous ensembles [104]. Still, most of the laser processing in application-
387 relevant cases deal with continuous cycling of a large ensemble of particles, which, in contact with
388 a liquid medium involves cooperative phenomena, such as heat dissipation, evaporation, creation
389 of shock waves or reorganization of formed products like fragmented clusters to new objects by
390 ripening. Therefore, it is important to understand and quantify such processes that may occur con-
391 comitantly and will affect each other.

Figure 6: A) Estimation of temperature change of slowly heated gold nanoparticles as function of absorbed laser energy, B) Calculation of the laser fluence required to convert excited gold NPs into the (partially S+L) molten state (L) or partially evaporated state (L+G) with 532 nm radiation with 10 ns pulse length as function of particle diameter. Figure 6 A is reprinted with permission from Ref. [46], Copyright 1999 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 6 B is reprinted from [47], A. Pyatenko et al., “Mechanism of pulse laser interaction with colloidal nanoparticles”, Laser & Photonics Reviews, with permission from John Wiley and Sons. © 2013 by WILEY-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

392 First we develop a basic hypothesis of how laser irradiation with significant energy deposition into
393 the system of interest (for example an aqueous colloid or solid surface in contact to liquid) should
394 lead to restructuring. In a simple model, the laser energy is converted into heat that will be local-
395 ized in the absorbing part within the laser penetration depth. Absorption is linear as expressed by
396 the (known) absorption cross section. In the model by Takami et al. [46], which is expected to hold
397 from nanosecond pulse excitation, the absorbed energy by the laser pulse is converted into lattice
398 temperature by taking the material heat capacity into account. Figure 6 A) shows the temperature

399 of heated gold NPs as function of absorbed laser energy. Once the temperature reaches the melting
400 point melting sets in. The amount of molten material is given by the additional available energy
401 beyond the heat capacity in the solid state to account for latent heat of melting [47,105], see calcu-
402 lations shown in Fig. 6 B). After full melting, the temperature of the particle will increase further
403 until the evaporation threshold is reached. Evaporation again requires additional energy to over-
404 come heat of fusion. Only evaporation can lead to expulsion of material and formation of clusters
405 in this context via condensation of the vapor. Further processes that will be described in the laser
406 ablation section, such as phase explosion do require fast heating for the material to leave the bin-
407 odal of liquid-gas coexistence and reach the critical point, respectively spinodal line [38].
408 This model offers a conceptually straightforward access into classifying structure formation ac-
409 cording to the maximally reached temperature after photo-excitation. However, it should not be
410 taken literally, if the excitation is done by shorter pulses in the picosecond range, where a sub-
411 stantial difference between electron and lattice temperature can take place. At the same time, the
412 melting process on the nanoscale will not be described by a steady-state process as on macroscopic
413 length scales. Melting as a heterogeneously driven phase transition may require nucleation, which
414 sets the time scale for the transition to the liquid state to some picoseconds in defective systems to
415 some hundreds of picoseconds in single-crystalline samples, which lack nucleation sites. Thus, a
416 transient overheating above the melting point could even take place, which lasts for 100 to 200 pi-
417 coseconds. On longer time scales heat dissipation can set in during the heating with nanosecond
418 or longer pulses. Heat dissipation in small NPs is strongly size dependent and can be as short as
419 100 ps from small particles < 20 nm. Steady-state evaporation is also inefficient for mass transport
420 on a picosecond to nanosecond time scale that is of interest here. Thus, thresholds for ablation and
421 fragmentation will shift to energies far above the energy required to reach the boiling point of the
422 irradiated material.

423 With these complications in mind, it is useful to take a closer look at the energy distribution path-
424 way. In almost all cases of linear absorbing materials the laser light interacts first with electrons
425 that excited them into a state far above the Fermi level.

426 These electrons thermalize within hundreds of fs to a temperature much higher than the lattice tem-
427 perature [108]. Under such a highly nonequilibrium condition, hot electrons transfer their energy
428 to the cool lattice of NPs through the electron-phonon coupling process. As the electron heat ca-
429 pacity is temperature-dependent in simple metals [28] (and scattering cross section decreases with
430 temperature) the cooling of the electron gas tends to slow down with increasing excitation den-
431 sity [109]. A well-known case is gold with exceptionally weak electron-phonon coupling, such
432 that the complete cooling of the electron gas could last for tens of picoseconds [23,110]. There-
433 fore, excitation with short pulses of picosecond duration or shorter would display transient differ-
434 ences between electronic and phonon subsystem. This selectively heated electron gas can instigate
435 processes other than purely thermal effects. Among these are electron emission [111], near-field
436 forces of the plasmon resonance on the surface or pressure effects due to an expanding electron gas
437 [25,27] or spatial spreading of fast electrons [112,113]. In general, with femtosecond excitation a
438 large fraction of electrons (in the order of 10 %) can be excited, which would lead to changes of

Figure 7: Ultrafast transient absorption data measuring the heat transfer from Au NPs to the liquid environment. A) Measurement result of time-resolved absorbance intensity for 15-nm-diameter Au NPs. B) Result for 4-nm-diameter Au NPs. For both cases, temperature rises of the laser-heated NPs are indicated inside the plots. Figure 7 is reprinted with permission from Ref. [87], Copyright 2002 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

439 the interatomic forces faster than electron-phonon coupling. This has been seen in semiconductors
 440 [24,114] in particular.

441 The electron-phonon coupling will increase the temperature of the lattice, which will undergo
 442 phase transitions when sufficient thermal energies are coupled to the lattice. Depending on the en-
 443 ergy density condition the lattice reaches, phase transitions can result in coalescence of multiple
 444 NPs [15,105], or transformation of NPs into vapor, atomic clusters, and small molten NPs. In both
 445 cases, the temperature difference between the hot NPs and the surrounding liquid drives heat trans-
 446 fer from the NPs to the liquid environment. This heat transfer process impacts the thermal equilib-
 447 rium within the NPs, thereby shaping their phase evolution pathway. Furthermore, the non-thermal
 448 effects that were described above can also play a role in the energy dissipation of the photo-excited
 449 NPs.

450 Thus, a description and verification of putative processes that lead to structure formation, such as
 451 NP formation after laser ablation or particle breakup in laser fragmentation requires sensitive tools
 452 for detecting and discerning the largely co-evolving processes. Given a time scale for electron tem-
 453 perature equilibration of few picoseconds to diffusive ripening processes of minutes to hours, the
 454 time-resolved tools require temporal resolution that spans many decades. Early experimental ef-
 455 forts focused on probing energy dissipation from metallic NPs to their liquid surroundings, em-
 456 ploying TAS [84-87]. This technique operates by exploiting the photo-excitation of free electrons
 457 within the NPs, which modulates the absorbance spectrum of the probe light. As the transmission
 458 through a macroscopic suspension containing NPs or reflection from a photo-excited NP is deter-
 459 mined by absorption as well as scattering, several structural processes may contribute to a change
 460 in signal.

461 Metal NPs show SPR linked to coherent excitation of electron in the conduction band. Its position

Figure 8: Examples for time-resolved optical studies of gold NP excitation. In (A) TAS with a pulsed pump beam and a continuous-wave probe beam is demonstrated for absorption contrast and imaging contrast, with a selected scattering image for a generated nanobubble (B) and transient transmission traces (C) for increasing laser fluence. Changes in optical extinction of 60 nm gold particles in water at 22 °C, 100 °C (D) and in vapor as well as additional contribution by light scattering from 60 and 125 nm vapor bubbles (E), respectively. Bubble sizes on excited NPs as function of applied fluence for nanosecond pulses (F) and femtosecond pulses (G). Figure 8 A-C are adapted with permission from Lukyanova-Hleb et al., ACS Nano [106], Copyright 2010 by American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figures 8 D-G are reprinted with permission from [107] (“Thermodynamics of nanosecond nanobubble formation at laser-excited metal nanoparticles“, © 2011 A. Siems et al., published by IOP Publishing, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 3.0 Unported License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

462 and width are given by the dielectric functions of metal and medium and described by Mie theory
 463 [115]. Mie theory allows to derive absolute absorption and scattering cross section of primarily
 464 spherical or core-shell objects, but also different shapes by extensions of Mie-Gans [116] theory or
 465 numerical approaches [117]. The subsequent pressure and temperature conditions emanate from
 466 the close interaction of the excited particles with the medium. The width of the SPR reflects the
 467 coherence time of this oscillation. This dephasing time amounts to a few femtoseconds, leading
 468 to plasmon resonance width of several tens of nanometers [118]. In turn, a strongly excited elec-
 469 tron gas leads to an increased scattering rate, which can be detected as plasmon broadening in TAS
 470 experiments.

471 A change of electron temperature manifests itself as a "bleach" in the surface plasmon band, ac-
 472 companied by a positive transient absorption signal near the bleached region, signifying the broad-
 473 ening. The decay dynamics of these signals are dictated by electron-phonon coupling within the
 474 particle and phonon-solvent interaction at the particle surface, hence informing about the overall
 475 energy relaxation timescales.

476 The application of transient absorption technique was nicely demonstrated in the work by Hu *et*
477 *al.* [87], in which they measured solvated NPs of varying sizes and determined the effect of size
478 on the rate of energy relaxation. As shown in Fig. 7 A), the transient bleach results for larger NPs
479 showed two distinct decay regions: (i) an initial fast decay due to electron-phonon coupling within
480 the particle, and (ii) a slow decay due to heat dissipation from the particle to the environment. It
481 was found that the relaxation times of heat dissipation were proportional to the square of the ra-
482 dius, but did not depend on the initial particle temperature. For smaller particles, as shown in Fig.
483 7 B), the results revealed that the timescale for heat dissipation was comparable to that of electron-
484 phonon coupling. This suggests significant energy loss had occurred before electrons and phonons
485 reached thermal equilibrium within the particle. It was proposed that the solvent molecules directly
486 interact with non-thermal electrons at the particle surface, particularly in very small particles.
487 In fact, the relatively well-defined geometry of NP colloids that leads to excitation localization
488 and uniformity as well as the understanding of the optical response of the SPR helped to clarify
489 specifics of electron dynamics and coupling to the phonons and close boundaries. Valleé, del Fatti
490 *et al.* [119,120] and others [121,122] addressed size effects of electron dynamics as well structural
491 relaxations by these model systems.

492 Electron emission has been verified in many nanoscale systems in vacuum, where the emission is
493 accessible. It is less straightforward to directly detect non-thermal effects as electron emission in
494 liquid medium. Mafuné and coworkers managed to record the spectral signature of solvated elec-
495 trons in water after massive excitation of silver NPs [123]. On the other hand, light emission can
496 be harnessed to access the local temperatures of molecules [124,125] or by using reporter fluo-
497 rophores that are sensitive on temperature [126].

498 Structure formation, such as lattice heating, melting or shape transformations, is normally consid-
499 ered to set in with electron thermalization with the lattice. Nevertheless, the hot electron gas can
500 exert structural forces on the lattice even before thermalization. Gold or silver NPs in particular
501 have displayed non-thermal effects upon excitation, such as directed fragmentation or near-field
502 ablation [26,52]. While electronic excitation is easily detected by TAS the various structural re-
503 sponses of NPs are weaker and ambiguous in TAS. While elastic oscillations of NPs are identified
504 in periodic modulation of the plasmon resonance due to the change of electron density other re-
505 sponses, such as particle heating or melting are less characteristic. In fact, pure heating of gold
506 particles leads to a very small change in SPR position [122], which is even modulated by an even-
507 tual change of the temperature of the surrounding liquid through a change of the refractive index
508 [107]. Light scattering becomes relevant if the structures exceed a size of a fraction of the wave-
509 length [106,127,128]. Fig. 8 A) shows several schemes of exciting NPs by focused laser beams for
510 excitation and probing. Both coaxially and from the side to image the scattering emitted from in-
511 duced nanobubbles [106] shown in fig. 8 B.

512 The SPR of liquid metal particles such as, for instance gold, should drastically change due the
513 change of the dielectric function. Nevertheless, the melting transition has never been detected spec-
514 troscopically on an ultrafast time scale. In thin-film geometry the optical reflectivity has been reli-
515 ably assigned to film melting [129,130]. Optical reflectivity is discussed in more detail in the fol-
516 lowing chapter.

517 Additionally, if the NP temperature is high enough, the heat released to the liquid within a few tens
518 of picoseconds can be sufficient to form vapor bubbles around the particles. In this case, the refrac-
519 tive index changes strongly, which leads to a strong shift and dampening of the SPR. Such calcula-
520 tion of the extinction for gold NPs in water for various water temperatures, including water vapor
521 is depicted in fig. 8 D) as well as the extinction of vapor bubbles (E). Although the change of water
522 temperature imposes only a minor change on the SPR, the formation of a bubble drastically reduces
523 the SPR height in a fashion similar to NP melting. For bubbles exceeding a diameter of 60 to 100
524 nm the transmission loss due to scattering becomes relevant, which in sum can lead to both positive
525 and negative transmission changes, as shown in fig. 8 C. Therefore, TAS at this point is no longer
526 an unambiguous probe for the resolution of such effects [131]. Nevertheless, the bubble formation
527 as a threshold process can still be identified through the characteristic change in transient absorp-
528 tion first through plasmon dampening and with increasing bubble size through the increase in scat-
529 tering once the bubble reaches some 100 nm in diameter. A quantitative analysis of the change of
530 the TAS signal as compared to Mie calculations can in some cases even reproduce the bubble for-
531 mation threshold as well as bubble sizes[107,128]. Figures 8 F) show that bubble size growth with
532 laser fluence can be extracted with good correlation to x-ray results (G).

533 As structure formation, such as LAL or LFL in NP colloids and on surfaces involves all steps of
534 particle heating, melting, evaporation or bubble formation of the surrounding liquid TAS alone is
535 not sufficient to identify all these steps. Scattering methods with short wavelength allow multiple
536 length scales to be resolved down to the atomic scale. UED, for instance, can resolve atomic-scale
537 structure formation [65,132] with picosecond time resolution, as described in the section about
538 liquid dynamics . The high interaction cross section is suitable for minuscule material quantities,
539 such as nanostructures [23], surface phenomena [133] or gases [134], but poses challenges in the
540 bulk condensed phase. X-ray scattering, on the other hand, penetrates matter deeper due to a cross
541 section that is 10^5 times smaller. Brilliant sources for pulsed x-rays are modern synchrotrons with
542 pulse lengths of about 60-100 ps at high repetition rate of some megahertz, which can be used in
543 time-resolved experiment by synchronized lasers to selected sub-pulses in the accelerators that
544 produce x-rays[135]. X-rays probe the electron density distribution that can be expressed as pair-
545 wise summation of pairs of scatterers of scattering length $f_i(q)$, see eq. 3, leading to the general no-
546 tion of the scattering distribution in q space being the Fourier transform squared of the real-space
547 scattering length distribution. As this scattering length is well known, scattering can be described
548 quantitatively in units of the electron scattering strength $r_0 = 2.8 \cdot 10^{-15}$ m.

549 NP materials, such as suspensions represent a heterogeneous system of several structural length
550 scales, all of which will be detected in an appropriate geometry and mass relation. Figure 9 shows
551 an example of different structural features that can be observed as function of q scale and thus the
552 inverse length scale after photo-excitation of a aqueous suspension of 53 nm gold particles. The
553 particles only occupy a mass fraction of 0.02 %. Fig. 9 (A) displays the relative changes in scatter-
554 ing, if the suspension is irradiated by 1 ps laser pulses at the interband transition at 400 nm. This
555 difference ΔI displays negative and positive contributions depending on the formation, disappear-
556 ance or shift of structural features. First, the Fourier transform of the complete particle leads to
557 small-angle scattering (SAXS) at low scattering vectors corresponding to π/D with D being the par-

558 ticle size. In part C) such a 2D depiction of ΔI^*q^2 is shown in false colors, where blue to red areas
559 indicate negative difference to positive difference. At the lowest observable q the change is nega-
560 tive, qualitatively indicating that the largest structure is lost due to photo-excitation due to particle
561 fragmentation [136]. Increased intensity at intermediate q ($0.1 - 0.6 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) reveals new structure for-
562 mation on the 1 to 5 nm scale, which is caused by the formation of clusters from the fragmentation
563 process.

Figure 9: (A) Change of x-ray scattering distribution of a laser-excited gold particle suspension in water at 400 nm over a wide scattering vector range q . The lowest range of q ($0.01 - 0.1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$) relates to the largest structures and their changes, such as fragmentation of the initial 50 nm particles or formation of concentric vapor bubbles, with the corresponding 2D difference scattering distribution shown in (C). Fragmented small particles appear a large q range of $0.1-0.5 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. The wide angle scattering region from 0.5 to $< 4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ is dominated by water scattering (D) which changes distinctly upon change of thermodynamic parameters. Finally, the crystalline lattice of gold produces narrow powder peaks corresponding to lattice planes (111) and (200) that react upon heating and/or melting of the lattice. The arrows in (A) indicate the loss of powder scattering due to particle fragmentation. A shift in peak position is indicative of particle heating and serves as a thermometer with a linear shift with applied fluence in (E). Figure 9 A is reprinted with permission from [137], Y. Pokhrel et al., J. Phys. Chem. C 2025, Copyright 2025 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 9 C is adapted with permission from [136], Copyright 2024 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figures 9 B, D and E were newly plotted using data from [136].

564 While the gold content in the sample is very low, the scattering over a wide range in q ($0.5 - > 4$
565 \AA^{-1}) is dominated by liquid scattering of water(part (D)). Due to the liquid order, the preferential
566 distances of oxygen in water cause the maxima around 2 and 2.8\AA^{-1} [138], as explained in the liq-
567 uid structural dynamics section. As discussed above, water is not a pure spectator to the gold ex-
568 citation but reacts by heating, bubble formation, compression or expansion, all of which will mod-
569 ify the scattering function. In the limit of weak perturbation of the structural degrees of freedom
570 the change in the scattering distribution can be considered as a sum of stationary functions ∂S re-
571 lated two independent thermodynamic variables within temperature T , pressure p and density ρ
572 [139,140].

$$573 \quad \Delta I(\rho, T, q) = \left. \frac{\partial S}{\partial T} \right|_{\rho} \cdot \Delta T + \left. \frac{\partial S}{\partial \rho} \right|_T \cdot \Delta \rho \quad (5)$$

574 These stationary functions are characteristic for any liquid and can be derived in control experi-
575 ments. Thus, the analysis of change in water scattering offers an access to the thermodynamic
576 state of the medium that hosts the NPs. The functions $\left. \frac{\partial S}{\partial \rho} \right|_T$ and $\left. \frac{\partial S}{\partial p} \right|_T$ are displayed in fig. 9 (A)
577 and are used to model the water scattering changes. Most prominently, bubble formation will lead
578 to a compression of the adjacent liquid water, such that the amplitude Δp of the function $\left. \frac{\partial S}{\partial p} \right|_T$ will
579 be proportional to the bubble volume [141,142]. Finally, the crystalline lattice of the gold parti-
580 cle produces Bragg peaks that scale in angular position with the inverse of the lattice parameter d .
581 These peaks are registered as powder rings, as the ensemble of NPs is not oriented in the liquid.
582 The width of the peaks depends inversely on the crystal grain size, while the integrated intensity
583 scales with the crystalline volume. In the data displayed in fig. 9 the experimental resolution is the
584 limiting factor to the peak width.
585 The powder scattering opens direct access to the thermodynamic state of the NPs with the tempera-
586 ture increase leading to a change of the lattice parameter:

$$587 \quad \frac{\Delta d}{d} = \alpha \Delta T \quad (6)$$

588 due to thermal expansion with expansion coefficient α (which could be temperature dependent) and
589 melting causing a loss in diffraction intensity. The change of the extracted (111) powder peak po-
590 sition with increasing fluence of excitation is shown in part (E). The peak shift at 40 J/m^2 can be
591 converted into temperature change by using thermal expansion coefficient and latent heat of gold
592 [30,136,143]. At 160 J/m^2 the peak has completely vanished proving melting of the particle due to
593 the absorption of energy. A quasi-linear variation of the excitation fluence immediately after photo-
594 excitation (delay 60 ps, the experimental time resolution) shows that this assumption holds over
595 a range of at least 1 % in expansion. Note that gold at the melting point of 1360 K would display
596 an expansion of 1.79 %. This is remarkably similar to the behavior of the gold particles, where
597 expansion is limited below 1.6 % and loss of powder scattering coincides with reaching this limit
598 [33,136]. Thus, a threshold fluence F_0 can be defined to reach the melting point of the particles by

599 extrapolating the quasi-linear expansion with fluence to the critical total expansion at the melting
600 point. This procedure serves to find an internal calibrant that defines the energy uptake scale in a
601 photo-excitation experiment. This can turn out to be important if either the absorption cross sec-
602 tion is not known due to sample modifications or experimental boundary conditions such as fluence
603 distributions or fluctuations are present. Transient bleaching or enhancement of absorption cross
604 section would as well cause a discrepancy between measured static cross section and energy ab-
605 sorption in a pulsed laser field [14,144].

606 All the different hierarchies of structure change due to energy dissipation are accessible in a time-
607 resolved x-ray experiment. The problem of describing the laser fragmentation process is manifold.
608 First, the energy scale has to be quantified to understand whether the process is thermally activated
609 or governed by non-thermal forces. Second, the evolution of length scales needs to be resolved to
610 quantify the grade of damage to the initial particles and the formation of new species like atoms,
611 clusters, and particles. Finally, the amount of interaction with the environment needs to be high-
612 lighted, which includes heat transfer or redox reactions. Simulations have earlier given a real-space
613 impression of how fragmentation could evolve in a photo-excited NP. MD simulations by Zhig-
614 ilei & Garrison [36] demonstrated that isolated (van der Waals bonded) NPs can be fragmented
615 by stress confinement for short pulses relative to the acoustic relaxation time (15 ps for 100 nm
616 particles), while excitation with relatively long pulses can lead to explosive thermal decomposi-
617 tion or phase explosion. This is also accompanied by an increase in the fluence required for frag-
618 mentation. Delfour & Itina [39] explore fragmentation by ultrashort laser pulses (0.15 ps) both by
619 thermal decomposition and Coulomb instability (see fig. 1 H). The latter can destabilize smaller
620 particles by photo-thermal ejection of electrons that induces shape instability [145] in the liquid
621 state. For larger particles a combination of stress-induced and thermal explosion is corroborated.
622 Finally, Huang et al. [44,45] develop a detailed model by large-scale simulations of gold particles
623 excited in water environment, including heat transfer and bubble formation. Excitation of 20 nm
624 particles by 10 ps laser pulses clearly presents a thermal fragmentation scenario, which evolves in
625 different regimes from a partial (weak) fragmentation with formation of large and small fragments
626 to a strong phase explosion that is described by a spinodal process. Moreover, the role of water is
627 pointed out, which accepts heat, but also suspends atoms and small clusters after rapid cooling but
628 repels ejected larger, hot particles that eventually would reform a large particle at the location of the
629 initial particle. This is ascribed to the so-called inverse Leidenfrost effect, whereby hot particles
630 that reach the vapor-liquid boundary are repelled by the formation of additional vapor in a similar
631 way to the way water droplets are repelled from a hot surface in the common Leidenfrost effect, or
632 on heated NPs [146]. As a result, fragmentation seems to be less efficient when only regarding the
633 final products rather than resolving intermediate structures.

634 Several experimental studies have addressed the fragmentation process both by recording transient
635 dynamics and carefully analyzing NPs generated after the fragmentation[147]. Werner et al. [51]
636 postulate a Coulomb instability [145,148] by transient increase of absorption due to formed nan-
637 oclusters and the post-mortem TEM analysis (see fig. 1 B-E). Melting can also be identified in
638 the final state by the rounding of initial facets on the particles and blue shift of the SPR[149,150].
639 Other studies focus on the polarization effect on fragmentation, which is indicative of directed frag-

640 mentation by forces induced by the incident laser polarization [151,152]. The notion is that field
641 emission of electrons forms the force field for directed fragmentation and collection of debris [52].
642 On the other hand, direct material ejection by the near-field has been described [26] as anisotropic
643 fragmentation channel in the absence of particle melting.

644 In the recent multiscale time-resolved x-ray experiments [136,142] the question of structural frag-
645 mentation pathways and mechanism is tackled by the information on size evolution by SAXS mea-
646 surements (fig. 10 A-B) resolving the time scale of reactions as well as the energy, resp. heat distri-
647 bution in the system. The latter is central for allowing to match the change of energy absorption by
648 a variable laser fluence with the large-scale simulations [45] as indicated in fig. 10 E. The matching
649 of absorbed energy ϵ in the simulations and the applied fluence F in the experiment is done at the
650 point, where the melting transition is reached, which is termed F_0 and easy to identify via thermal
651 expansion as explained above.

652 Under the premise that thermal heating of the excited NPs is directly proportional to the applied
653 external fluence one can relate the structural reactions found at a given fluence scale to the struc-
654 tural snapshots from the MD simulations (fig. 10 D, E). In particular, the number and sizes of frag-
655 ments can be deduced from the experiment and compared to the simulation. Fig. 10 A reveals that
656 the change of the size of the initial particle and the number and sizes of the produced fragments
657 follow a characteristic change as function of fluence. The gold NPs survive laser excitation with-
658 out damage, even if the fluence allows for transient melting. Only at 3-4 F_0 the particles starts to
659 get reduced in size. This is explained in the MD by a weak surface evaporation and beginning of
660 partial fragmentation. Although at higher fluence the MD simulations show a fragmentation in
661 pieces after increasing the internal energy at $9 \epsilon_0$ these fragments fuse again after the mentioned
662 inverse Leidenfrost effect. Thus, a full fragmentation with formation of uniformly sized clusters is
663 achieved only at $12 \epsilon_0$ or 12-15 F_0 in the experiment.

664 The aspect of necessary time scales in the scattering experiments needs to be addressed. If the for-
665 mation of a nanoparticle or a spatial distortion of a certain size develops with speed of sound, that
666 would set a shortest time scale worth resolving, which lies in the range of 3 - 30 ps for formed ob-
667 jects of 10 - 100 nm diameter. Thus, few picoseconds are appropriate to resolve the nascence of
668 nanoparticles in an ensemble, with the 60 ps available at synchrotrons coming close [135]. On the
669 other hand, single-particle experiments can take advantage of much higher time resolution, if struc-
670 tural changes within single addressed particles happen on a sub-picosecond time scale as discussed
671 above. At the same time, detection of small clusters in a diluted system such as in suspensions or
672 liquid during LAL is limited because of the rapid decrease of scattering cross section (scales with
673 the volume V^2). In time-resolved SAXS this limit has been seen at about 1 nm in diameter for gold
674 [136].

675 The experiments also show that the transient structuring is by far not the final state of the fragmen-
676 tation process, as the clusters are still at close distance (fig. 10 E) and can aggregate again. In fact,
677 ripening is found to occur on the microsecond time scale and will lead to a different final state that
678 could be observed in static analysis of the final state. Manipulating this ripening therefore requires
679 intervention on a fast time scale or a strong dilution of the particles through fragmentation. The
680 addition of electrolytes was shown to be efficient in collecting the smallest possible clusters after

681 fragmentation [12]. Alternatively, supporting the clusters on a substrate [153] or embedding in a
682 matrix [52] could also reduce ripening.

Figure 10: Caloric progress of gold NP heating and fragmentation as result of picosecond-resolved x-ray scattering experiments (A-C) and simulations (E) as function of laser fluence F and deposited energy per atom in the experiment and simulations, respectively. The scale of energy deposition is scaled by the fluence F_0 , respectively energy per atom ϵ_0 to reach the melting point (energy scale in D). (A) The initial spherical particles of 44 nm diameter stay intact after undergoing a melting transition above an F/F_0 of 1.43 up to 4 (higher than reaching the boiling point T_b at 1.05 eV or 3.5 F/F_0) at a $1 \mu\text{s}$ delay (400 nm), before being reduced in size gradually to vanish at 15 F/F_0 . At the same time, clusters of 2 to 3 nm in diameter appear to end in complete fragmentation, when the initial particles have vanished. (B) Fragment sizes are found to cluster around 3 nm with some remaining large fragments upon incomplete fragmentation at 532 nm. (C) The fragmented clusters would ripen through fusion and addition of active species on a microsecond scale, which can be partly suppressed by salt addition. (D) Mapping of the fluence scale as established in the experiment through identification of F_0 on the energy scale of nanoparticle heating in the MD simulations including melting temperature T_m and boiling temperature T_b . (E) Final state of simulations of 20 nm particles with increasing energy deposition, which reproduce the observations of complete recrystallization below 0.7 eV/atom followed by weak phase explosion (1.8) and formation of large fragments (2.7) that merge again (2.7 eV) and finally full fragmentation through a strong phase explosion at 3.6 eV/atom. The color coding shows temperature at 0.3 and 0.7 eV/atom and cluster size in number of atoms for 1.8–3.6 eV/atom. Figures 10 A, D and E are adapted with permission from [136], Copyright 2024 American Chemical Society. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figures 10 B-C were adapted from [142] (“In situ structural kinetics of picosecond laser-induced heating and fragmentation of colloidal gold spheres“, © 2020 A. R. Ziefuss et al., published by RSC, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

683 **Large scale optical probing of laser ablation dynamics in liquids**

684 In contrast to the fragmentation of NPs, typically homogeneous bulk samples are excited by the
685 laser source during (LAL) to produce higher amounts of NP. Here, the diameter of the laser excited
686 area lies typically in the range of a few tens of microns because the geometrical dimension of the
687 optical setup and liquid cuvettes demand focusing distances of a few hundred mm. Since the dy-
688 namical processes initiated after laser pulse impact occur on timescales ranging from picoseconds
689 to nanoseconds, with the fastest processes occurring on a sub-picosecond timescale, a high tem-
690 poral dynamic range combined with high temporal resolution is of paramount importance for the
691 experimental investigation of laser ablation. Optical probing methods fulfill this criterion with the
692 disadvantage of a lower spatial resolution of several hundred nm compared to X-ray examination
693 due to their longer wavelength. The great advantage of optical probing is the possibility to image
694 the laser ablation process time-resolved from the surface or from the side and to gain quantitative
695 spatial and temporal information about the optical reflection and absorption to validate existing
696 models and to gain a fundamental understanding of the laser ablation process. In the following sec-
697 tions, we will start with a brief introduction of laser ablation in air (LAA), where different optical
698 probing techniques are introduced and compared regarding their resolution and obtainable physical
699 quantities. This is followed by an in-depth review of using optical probing techniques to obtain a
700 concise picture of LAL dynamics on timescales ranging from picoseconds up to microseconds.

701 **Laser ablation in air**

702 Laser ablation of metals with ultrashort pulses (USPs) takes place as a cascade of ultrafast pro-
703 cesses: After the initial absorption of the laser pulse within the optical penetration depth, electronic
704 thermalization via electron-electron scattering is leading to a sharp increase in electron temper-
705 atures within a few to tens of femtoseconds [154,155]. Due to the comparatively slow electron-
706 phonon coupling, the heating of the lattice is delayed by about 1 ps to 20 ps, depending on the ma-
707 terial [156-158]. In parallel, strongly temperature-dependent electron transport [159] drives spatial
708 heat flow, with typically two distinct regimes of heat diffusion [160]. The theoretical description
709 of these processes is carried out mainly using the TTM, which describes the energy flows between
710 the electron and phonon subsystems using coupled Fourier equations [20]. This applies to pulse
711 lengths that exceed the electron-electron thermalization time and fall below the electron-phonon
712 interaction time. For typical lattice heating rates of about 1 kK/ps, isochoric heating leads to a
713 pressure increase of several GPa, provided the stress confinement condition is met [50,161-163].
714 Depending on the fluence, these high stresses lead to different ablation mechanisms: Near the ab-
715 lation threshold, photo-mechanically initiated spallation occurs, where a thin liquid layer of a few
716 nanometers is ablated by mechanical fracture after the formation of subsurface voids due to exten-
717 sive tensile stresses [38,49,50,161]. If the temperature exceeds about 0.9 of the thermodynamic
718 critical temperature, a photo-thermal phase explosion occurs in which the material decomposes
719 by explosive boiling into a mixture of vapor and liquid droplets [24,164-166]. At even higher flu-
720 ence values, the ablation plume can be ionized and forms plasma-like states, such as those utilized
721 in pulsed laser deposition [167]. For pulse durations exceeding the stress confinement condition,

722 the ablation process becomes rather fluence-independent and is primarily photo-thermal [161,168].
723 The mechanisms of these process dynamics can only be understood fully by a combination of sim-
724 ulations with suitable pump-probe techniques, which provide time-resolved observables and post-
725 ablation metrics. Common pump-probe methods and their results are presented in the following.

726 **Summary of common pump-probe methods using laser ablation in air as an** 727 **example**

728 The dynamics of USP laser ablation on time scales of femtoseconds to picoseconds exceed the tem-
729 poral resolution of conventional optical sensors, whose integration times are typically in the range
730 of nanoseconds to milliseconds. As early as 1967, Shelton et al. [169] used an optical USP pump-
731 probe setup for the first time to investigate the lifetimes of color centers in crystals by means of
732 transmission measurements. The basic principle - a pump pulse and a split, time-delayed probe
733 pulse that scans the transient change in the target using an optical delay line - is still used today
734 [170].

735 Pump-probe measurements to study the interactions between femtosecond laser pulses and bulk tar-
736 gets, were first presented in 1983 by Shank et al. [171,172] and Eesley [173]. These early works,
737 which were not yet imaging, focused on time-dependent reflectance changes to investigate pro-
738 cesses such as the heating of electrons and lattice in copper [173]. In this way, deeper insights
739 could be gained into the TTM introduced by Anisimov in 1974 [20]. In addition, the metallic prop-
740 erties of liquid silicon made it possible to observe phase transitions such as melting [172].

741 In subsequent years, the non-equilibrium dynamics between electrons and phonons were mainly in-
742 vestigated using pump-probe reflectometry – under induced temperature changes of a few to several
743 thousand Kelvin. This research, often in combination with theoretical modeling, focused primarily
744 on metals [174-179]. In addition, USP laser-induced phase transitions in semiconductors have been
745 investigated [129], and first mechanistic material responses, such as early hydrodynamic motions at
746 lattice heating rates of up to kK/ps, have been observed [180].

747 The first imaging method, pump-probe microscopy (PPM), was introduced in 1984 by Downer et
748 al. [181]. With a temporal resolution of about 100 fs and imaging on photographic paper, the au-
749 thors succeeded in imaging the laser-induced melting and evaporation process in silicon both spa-
750 tially and temporally. In the late 1990s, Von der Linde and Sokolowski-Tinten et al. [182] carried
751 out systematic PPM experiments to investigate the dynamics of the ablation process in dielectrics,
752 semiconductors and metals. Newton rings were observed for the first time during the ablation of
753 metals and silicon, whose temporal extent could be limited to intervals of a few 100 ps to a few
754 ns [24]. However, at that time, these phenomena were not associated with spallation but were at-
755 tributed to an expanding inhomogeneous phase. It was not until 2006 that Bonse et al. [183] -
756 based on work by Zhakhovskii et al. [184] - provided an interpretation that corresponds to the cur-
757 rent state of the art.

758 In 2012, Domke et al. [185] published an extended PPM setup that includes an electronically de-
759 layed laser alongside an optical delay. This enabled delay times above several nanoseconds up to
760 the second scale, with a temporal resolution of 0.5 ns. In recent years, the PPM methodology has

761 been widely used to investigate a wide variety of systems during USP laser ablation. These inves-
762 tigations cover dielectrics and semiconductors [186,187], metals and alloys [160,170,188-190] as
763 well as transparent and metallic thin films [191-194].

764 The PPM method used for studying laser ablation typically employs an ultrashort pump pulse in
765 the near-IR at wavelengths of about 800 nm (Ti:Sapphire laser) or 1030 nm (Yb doped laser) with a
766 pulse duration in the sub-ps to the ps range to initiate the ablation process and a time-delayed probe
767 pulse, which is often generated by frequency doubling of a part of the pump pulse.

768 The temporal resolution of the method is determined by the duration of the probe pulse. For an
769 “ultrafast movie”, a separate experiment is carried out on a pristine target area for each delay time,
770 especially when irreversible changes of the target are involved. Delay times up to the nanosecond
771 scale (corresponding to an optical path of approx. 30 cm for 1 ns) are realized using optical delay
772 lines; for larger delays, electronically synchronized lasers are employed [185]. This flexibility al-
773 lows the investigation of dynamics over nine orders of magnitude.

774 The lateral resolution is limited by the probe wavelength and is typically around 0.5 μm for the fre-
775 quency doubled NIR probe pulses, while the pump beam diameter can vary from a few microme-
776 ters to several hundred micrometers.

777 Various optical probing techniques have been developed based on the pump-probe principle. These
778 range from microscopy (PPM) and reflectometry (PPR) [193] to shadowgraphy (PPS) [195,196] -
779 in which transient quantities such as reflectivity, absorption and transmission are investigated - to
780 more complex methods such as pump-probe ellipsometry (PPE) [197] to determine the complex
781 refractive index and interferometry (PPI) [198,199] to measure temporal phase changes, material
782 bulges and spallation layer velocities. As explained below, some of these techniques are subject to
783 specific limitations regarding the time window accessible for measurements.

784 Figure 11A shows a typical PPM setup for capturing the time-resolved reflectivity of the ablation
785 area over the entire temporal range. The pump pulse (red) is applied to the target at a defined an-
786 gle, while the time-delayed probe pulse (green) is imaged via polarization and frequency-selective
787 optics and a microscope objective to a camera.

788 Figure 11B shows exemplary PPM measurements using the example of stainless steel, performed
789 at approximately twice the ablation threshold and a pulse duration of 120 fs [190]. The time-
790 dependent relative reflectance change for different delay times is shown. Already within the first
791 picoseconds, a sharp drop in reflectance - caused by temperature and density changes as well as a
792 melting transition [156,200] - is visible, which leads to deep insights into non-equilibrium driven
793 electronic transport and hydrodynamic processes [160,201,202].

794 For delay times between 250 ps and 800 ps, characteristic interference patterns called Newton rings
795 appear in the crater center, which are caused by interference between the spallation layer and the re-
796 maining target [170,183,190]. These interference patterns determine the spallation layer velocities
797 to about 1 km/s [170,190,202], as well as the spatial extent of the spallation layer [186,190], both
798 depending on the fluence of the pump pulse.

799 In the phase explosion regime, the strongly absorbing and scattering ablation plume causes the al-
800 most complete reflectance to drop to zero, typically within 100 ps [163,168,192,203].

801 In addition, PPM enables the observation of the melting process in semiconductors, which is char-
802 acterized by the metallic properties of liquid semiconductors and the associated significant increase
803 in reflectance [181,204]. The method also allows analysis of the propagation of shock waves in
804 transparent materials [205] or at the air-target interface [195].

805 Pump-probe ellipsometry (PPE) proves to be an extremely powerful tool to get access to the ab-
806 sorptance and the reflectance of the surface [194,197,206-208]. PPE gives feasible values as long
807 as the Fresnel approximation at the surface is valid, which holds as long as structural changes
808 within the optical penetration depth are small [200]. That is typically the case for the delay times
809 up to 50 ps. As early as 1974, PPE was introduced by Auston et al. [206], even before the de-
810 velopment of PPM, to investigate the time-dependent generation of free charge carriers in laser-
811 irradiated germanium. Figure 11C shows a more contemporary rotating analyzer PPE setup, based
812 on the work of Rapp et al. [197].

813 For investigations on bulk targets, the measured time-dependent ellipsometric angles are typically
814 calculated into complex refractive indices using the pseudo-dielectric function [209]. PPE thus
815 provides two measured variables for each delay time, the real and imaginary components of the
816 complex refractive index.

817 Figure 11D illustrates an exemplary PPE measurement of the complex refractive index of alu-
818 minum, irradiated with a 500 fs laser pulse at various multiples of the ablation threshold [202].
819 As indicated here, the measurement is limited to a delay time of 40 ps, provided that structural
820 changes, such as spallation or phase explosion, remain within the Fresnel constraints. Such mea-
821 surements are usually considerably more complex to analyze than PPM data, as they require com-
822 prehensive modeling to obtain reliable and quantitative information about the process dynamics,
823 such as electron and lattice temperatures or density [200].

824 An extension to PPM is the so-called pump-probe interferometry (PPI) [198,199]. With this
825 method, not only the intensity, but also the phase of the probe pulse can be captured during the
826 ablation process, which enables investigations of surface bulging, for example before the spallation
827 process, with an accuracy in the nanometer range.

828 Technically, the method is realized by integrating a Michelson interferometer into the probe path
829 of a PPM setup, as shown in figure 11E. This causes interference lines on the detector, which are
830 due to the tilt of the reference arm relative to the target arm (see figure 11F, left graph) [198]. The
831 modulated lines contain the spatial phase information (figure 11F, right graph) [199].

832 These phase shifts can be caused by both time-varying optical properties of the target and optical
833 path differences of the bulging surface. Therefore, the analysis requires accurate modeling and pre-
834 cise temporal boundaries [198]. Combining measurements of the complex refraction index by PPE
835 and optical phase shift in the context of PPI with a validated model could offer new possibilities in
836 the future to resolve density and temperature on an ultrafast time scale.

837 A further variation of PPM is pump-probe shadowgraphy (PPS). This technique has proven to be
838 extremely powerful, particularly in LAL, in creating lateral images of the transmission of ablation
839 plumes, shock dynamics and bubbles [195,196,210-214]. The side illumination shown in figure
840 11G with a lateral resolution of about 1 μm makes it possible for the first time to visualize pro-

841 cesses in the nanosecond range, since shock or spallation fronts expand at speeds in the range of
 842 km/s.

843 Figure 11H shows an example of a typical PPS measurement on stainless steel. The plasma ioniza-
 844 tion front, the shock front in air and a strongly absorbing ablation plume in the center can be seen
 845 [196]. Especially for the analysis of the ablation plume on nanosecond timescales and with respect
 846 to its interaction with subsequent pulses of GHz or MHz bursts, PPS proves to be an extremely ef-
 847 fective tool [215-217].

848 Usually, the combination of different experimental techniques leads to a more comprehensive,
 849 quantitative understanding of the processes, which can be further matched with simulation data.

850 While the ablation process of metals in air has already been investigated intensively, new effects are
 851 emerging for LAL.

Figure 11

Figure 11 (*previous page*): (A) Schematic setup of for PPM. The pump pulse (red) is focused on the target at a defined angle, while the time-delayed probe pulse (green) is imaged through polarization and frequency-selective optics and a microscope objective on a CCD camera. (B) Time-resolved PPM measurements on stainless steel at a pump pulse duration of 120 fs and approximately twice the ablation threshold. The time-dependent change in reflection is shown for delay times from 360 fs to 1 s. Noticeable are Newton rings that form due to interference between the spallation layer and the underlying target. (C) Schematic diagram of PPE. A rotating analyzer enables the measurement of the ellipsometric angles used to determine the transient complex refractive index of the target. (D) PPE measurements of the complex refractive index of aluminum, irradiated with 500 fs long laser pulses. (E) Setup of PPI. A Michelson interferometer is integrated into the probe path to generate interference fringes on the CCD detector. The fringes contain the spatial phase information that provides information about surface bulging. (F) Typical PPI measurement. Left: Measured interference fringes caused by the tilt of the reference arm relative to the target arm. Right: Reconstructed phase or surface curvature as a function of position. (G) Schematic diagram of PPS. Shock fronts and ablation plumes can be visualized by lateral illumination with a lateral resolution of about $1 \mu\text{m}$. (H) PPS measurement on stainless steel. The plasma ionization front, the shock front in air and the strongly absorbing ablation plume in the center are shown. Figure 11 B is reprinted from [190], (© 2022 The Authors, some rights reserved; exclusive licensee John Wiley & Sons, Inc., distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 11 D is reprinted from [202], Applied Surface Science, vol. 511, by J. Winter et al., "Ultrafast Pump-Probe Ellipsometry and Microscopy Reveal the Surface Dynamics of Femtosecond Laser Ablation of Aluminium and Stainless Steel", pages 145514, Copyright (2020) with permission from Elsevier. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 11 F is reprinted from [199] (© 2024 T. Pflug et al., published by Springer Nature, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). Figure 11 H was reprinted with permission from [196] © Optical Society of America. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figures 11 A, C, E and G were inspired by [197]

Optical probing of laser ablation in liquid dynamics

In contrast to LAA, LAL is performed by immersing a target under a liquid layer with the aim of generating ligand-free NPs from virtually any material [1]. For this, most commonly ultrashort pulses with durations from several 100 fs to 10 ps or short pulses with pulse durations of about 10 ns are used. The liquid layer can either be an organic or an inorganic solvent. While the inorganic solvent water is most commonly used, organic solvents are desirable when processing oxidation-sensitive targets [19]. Furthermore, additives such as NaCl can be added in μM concentrations to the solvent to promote electrostatic stabilization of the produced NPs and prevent ripening within the liquid environment [218]. The liquid layer not only acts as the suspension medium for the generated NPs, but also allows control over NP properties [4,19] and facilitates high lattice cooling rates of up to 10 K/ps [33,107,219] promoting the generation of defect-rich NPs [220]. However, the presence of the liquid layer facilitates laser energy losses [221] and alters the ablation dynamics on all timescales ranging from ps to ms [222].

In the following section we will focus on water as an immersion medium and summarize the ablation dynamics induced by laser pulses as deduced by optical probing methods. These dynamics are presented chronologically, starting with the non-linear interaction of the laser pulse with the liquid top layer, followed by the ablation dynamics in the sub-nanosecond and nanosecond/microsecond range.

Pulse energy losses within the liquid layer

In LAA laser pulse energy can be delivered to the sample material without significant energy loss, as even for pulse durations of 120 fs optical breakdown within air is only observed for very high fluences exceeding 26 J/cm^2 [223]. These fluences are far above typical values employed in LAA, which lie for an efficient process in the range of several J/cm^2 corresponding to a few multiples of the ablation threshold [224]. For LAL on the other hand, the liquid immersion layer causes linear absorption losses. For example, water exhibits an absorption coefficient of 0.144 1/cm [225] at a laser wavelength of 1064 nm, thus resulting in linear absorption losses of several percent for typical water layers of several mm thickness.

Furthermore, the pulse intensities can create non-linear effects including filamentation [226] (see figure 12A) and optical breakdown [227] (see figure 12B). The lack of inversion symmetry in liquids gives rise to a third-order non-linear susceptibility $\chi^{(3)}$ facilitating degenerate four-wave mixing, resulting in self-focusing and self-phase modulation [226]. For femtosecond pulses, self-focusing is typically observed in liquids for peak powers of approximately 1 MW [228]. Importantly, it is the beam power and not the intensity that determines the onset of self-focusing [226,229]. Whole-beam self-focusing leads to a distortion of the beam profile and, exceeding a certain threshold, to an optical breakdown. Small-scale distortions in the spatial beam profile give rise to the development of filaments [230]. It was reported that this filamentation process can result in an absorption of up to 46% [231]. In the case of optical breakdown, a plasma with an electron density of typically 10^{21} cm^{-3} is generated within the liquid once threshold intensities in the range of several 10^{12} W/cm^2 for fs pulses [232], several 10^{11} W/cm^2 for ps pulses [233] and several

891 10^{10} W/cm² for ns pulses [233] are exceeded. The plasma generation within the liquid is driven
892 by either multi-photon absorption (fs pulse duration) or cascade ionization (ns pulse duration) or
893 a combination of both processes (ps pulse duration) [234]. Both lead to vaporization of the liq-
894 uid followed by shockwave and cavitation bubble (CB) emission [227] (see figure 12A). Reported
895 absorption losses due to optical breakdown within the liquid range from up to 30% at six times
896 the breakdown threshold for a 10 ps pulse, to 70% at 60 times the breakdown threshold for few ps
897 pulses [235]. This demonstrates that optical breakdown presents a significant loss mechanism in
898 LAL.

899 A way to circumvent this is simultaneous spatial and temporal focusing, resulting, enabling to dou-
900 ble LAL productivity compared to conventional optical systems [231]. Finally, alongside others,
901 self-phase modulation leads to a broadening of the laser pulse spectrum, which may be utilized for
902 super-continuum generation [236]. These processes demonstrate that the liquid layer already limits
903 the available pulse energy before the laser pulse impacts the target material. Once the laser pulse
904 energy reaches the target surface, dynamics are triggered, which differ significantly between LAL
905 and LAA as outlined in the next section.

906 **Sub-nanosecond laser ablation in liquid dynamics**

907 Once the laser pulse reaches the targets surface, the pulse energy is absorbed by the electronic sub-
908 system [237]. As is the case for LAA, here the absorption is also strongly fluence-dependent and
909 pulse-duration dependent, as the leading edge of the laser pulse heats the target sufficiently to al-
910 ter its optical properties, which in turn influences the absorptance for the trailing edge of the laser
911 pulse [238]. This phenomenon known as self-reflection may alter the absorptance of the target by
912 up to one order of magnitude compared to the low-fluence absorptance value [238,239]. Follow-
913 ing absorption of the laser pulse energy by the electron sub-system, the energy is transferred to the
914 lattice by electron-phonon coupling [237] on a timescale determined by the electron-phonon re-
915 laxation time which is of the order of 1 ps for strongly coupling targets such as stainless steel and
916 10 ps for weakly coupling targets such as Cu [202]. Up until this point, the laser energy absorption
917 and temperature equilibration are comparable for LAA and LAL [222].

918 Recent experimental works on LAL highlighted that the influence of the liquid overlayer is already
919 detectable a few ps before and after delay time zero. As shown in figure 12C, the reflectance for ab-
920 lation of Au for LAA with a 3 ps pulse drops and rises within a range of relative reflectance change
921 of $\Delta R/R_0 \approx -10\%$ to $\Delta R/R_0 \approx +10\%$, whereas for ablation in water a non-linear decrease to
922 about $\Delta R/R_0 \approx -85\%$ is observed faster than the laser pulse duration [158]. Similar reflectance dy-
923 namics were also observed for the ablation of Fe in water with a pulse duration of 500 fs [189]. In
924 the case of LAA, the drop and rise in reflectance shortly before and after pulse impact is attributed
925 to increasing temperature and decreasing density [200,202,240]. For LAL on the other hand, de-
926 tailed investigation of the fast reflectance decrease by PPM [158,189] showed that thermionic elec-
927 tron emission from the hot target generates a sufficient amount of free electrons within the liquid
928 to induce an optical breakdown closely above the targets surface. While this effect could be clearly
929 identified by the time-resolved optical experiments, its influence on key LAL outcomes such as ab-
930 lation efficiency and particle size distribution is still unknown.

Figure 12

Figure 12 (*previous page*): Sub nanosecond laser ablation dynamics in liquid. (A) Filament formation after irradiation of distilled water with a wavelength of 775 nm, a pulse duration of 150 fs and a pulse energy of 785 μJ . The laser pulse was incident from the left. (B) Optical breakdown formation after irradiation of distilled water with a wavelength of 1064 nm, a pulse duration of 30 ps and a pulse energy of 1 mJ. The image was taken 44 ns after the laser pulse incident from the left. (C) Relative reflectance change $\Delta R/R_0$ as a function of the delay time Δt following irradiation of a gold sample immersed in air (black) and water (blue) with a wavelength of 1056 nm, a pulse duration of 3 ps and peak fluences of $1.5 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$ (squares) and $3.0 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$ (circles). Here Φ_{thr} denotes the single-pulse ablation threshold fluence. (D) and (E) Snapshots of MD simulations of a FeNi target immersed in water irradiated with a 10 ps laser pulse with absorbed peak fluences of 0.08 J/cm^2 (D) and 0.135 J/cm^2 (E). (F) Snapshots of MD simulations of a bulk Au target immersed in water irradiated with a 100 fs laser pulse with an absorbed peak fluence of 0.4 J/cm^2 . (G) Normalized NP weight distribution produced by double-pulse ablation of gold in water with a 1064 nm, 10 ps and 13 J/cm^2 laser. Two inter-pulse spacings of 0 ps and 600 ps are shown. (H) Snapshots of MD simulations of a bulk Ag target immersed in water irradiated with a 100 fs laser pulse with an absorbed peak fluence of 0.3 J/cm^2 . Fig 12 A was adapted from [228] (© 2022 D. C. K. Rao et al., published by Springer Nature, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>). Figure 12 B was adapted with permission from [241] A. Vogel et al., "Shock wave emission and cavitation bubble generation by picosecond and nanosecond optical breakdown in water", *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 100, pages 148-165, 1996. Copyright 1996, Acoustical Society of America. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 12 C is reprinted from [158] (© 2022 M. Spelauge et al., published by Springer Nature, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>). Figures 12 D and E are reprinted with permission from [219] (C. Chen et al., "Atomistic modeling of pulsed laser ablation in liquids: spatially and time-resolved maps of transient nonequilibrium states and channels of nanoparticle formation", *Applied Physics A*, vol. 129, article number 288, published by Springer Nature, 2023, reproduced with permission from SNCSC). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 12 F is adapted from [242] (N.A. Inogamov et al., "Dynamics of Gold Ablation into Water", *Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Physics*, vol. 127, pages 79-106, 2018, adapted with permission from SNCSC). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. with permission from SNCSC, copyright 2018. Figure 12 G was used with permission from [243] ("Double-pulse laser ablation in liquids: nanoparticle bimodality reduction by sub-nanosecond interpulse delay optimization", by C. Doñate-Buendia et al., *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, vol. 56, issue 10, article no. 104001, published on 22 February 2023; <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/acbaaa>); © 2023 IOP Publishing Ltd; permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. All rights reserved. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 12 H is adapted from [244], C.-Y. Shih et al., "Generation of Subsurface Voids, Incubation Effect, and Formation of Nanoparticles in Short Pulse Laser Interactions with Bulk Metal Targets in Liquid: Molecular Dynamics Study", *J. Phys. Chem. C*, Copyright 2017 American Chemical Society, distributed under the ACS AuthorChoice/Editors' Choice via Creative Commons CC-BY Usage Agreement, https://pubs.acs.org/page/policy/authorchoice_ccby_termsfuse.html. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

931 These early phenomena are followed by the expansion and the ablation of material. Experimental
932 and computational works have identified photo-mechanical and photo-thermal ablation mecha-
933 nisms for LAA [161,245]. For peak fluences ranging from the ablation threshold Φ_{thr} to approx-
934 imately $2 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$ photo-mechanical spallation is the driving ablation mechanism [240]. Here, iso-
935 choric heating of the target within the regime of stress confinement [50,161] leads to the generation
936 of compressive shockwaves that reflect at the free surface of the heated volume, thereby producing
937 tensile stresses on the order of 10 GPa [161]. These stresses are sufficiently strong to overcome the
938 tensile strength of the material and cause fracture and ejection of a molten layer [246]. In addition
939 to spallation, such laser-driven shockwaves have been shown to induce phase transitions, for exam-
940 ple the transformation of graphite into diamond under nanosecond shock compression at pressures
941 exceeding 50 GPa [247]. A related industrial application is laser shock peening, which employs
942 shockwaves generated under a liquid confinement layer to induce plastic deformation and residual
943 compressive stresses that enhance the fatigue resistance and mechanical durability of metal sur-
944 faces without causing ablation [248]. In the relative reflectance change in figure 12C (black dots),
945 the spallation process specifically manifests at a peak fluence of $1.5 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$ as a slowly decaying
946 non-zero reflectance between 10 ps and 200 ps due to finite reflectance of the propagating spalla-
947 tion layer [158]. The spallation front can be monitored by time-resolved optical probing with the
948 appearance of Newton rings [24]. These rings arise due to interference of the probe pulse between
949 the upward propagating spallation layer and the underlying surface [249]. The deduced spallation
950 layer velocities are strongly fluence dependent and range from hundreds of m/s closely above the
951 ablation threshold fluence [190] to nearly 2 km/s at $2.5 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$ [202]. Notably, the Newton rings can
952 only be observed when the ejected spallation layer is thin enough to be partially transmissive for
953 the employed probe wavelength, which is typically the case when the spallation layer thickness is
954 comparable to the optical penetration depth [170]. When applying peak fluences larger than $2 \cdot \Phi_{\text{thr}}$,
955 the laser pulse heats the targets surface to temperatures close to the critical temperature and photo-
956 thermal phase explosion is initiated [250]. Here, the material decomposes into liquid droplets and
957 vapor [161]. In the PPM signal in figure 12C (black open circles) this mechanism is observed by
958 the drop of reflectance to 0 ($\Delta R/R_0 = -1$) after 100 ps due to scattering and multiple absorption of
959 probe pulse in the droplet/vapor mixture [158]. As this short overview shows, the ablation mecha-
960 nisms of spallation and phase explosion were extensively studied for LAA.

961 Similar ablation mechanisms are also expected to occur for LAL [158,219,222,244]. However, in
962 the case of LAL the material expands against the liquid layer, which in turn exerts recoil forces
963 on the ablated material and decelerates it [242,244]. This can be indirectly monitored by PPM as
964 shown in figure 12C (blue circles). Here for LAL the transient reflectance in the delay time range
965 of 20 ps to 200 ps exhibits a non-zero value independent of the applied peak fluence, implying
966 that a Fresnel-like boundary is present between the liquid layer and the emerging ablation plume
967 [158,189]. This shows the confinement of a liquid ablated material layer also at the higher fluence
968 (open blue circles, figure 12C) in the phase explosion regime by the surrounding water, since a
969 drop of the reflectance to -1 (zero reflectance) would be expected without the presence of the liquid
970 layer [158,245,251]. As shown in figure 12D, the confinement of the ablation plume is predicted
971 by MD simulations for ablation of $\text{Fe}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}$ within the spallation regime [219]. Here, the ejected

972 spallation layer is confined by the liquid and eventually redeposited to the target surface, while only
973 a small amount of ablated material is converted into NPs and clusters. Notably, the timescale for
974 the confinement from about 50 ps to 500 ps agrees well between the computational predictions
975 (figure 12D) and experimental observations (figure 12C). Furthermore, when moving to the phase
976 explosion regime (figure 12E) the MD simulations again predict the confinement of the ablation
977 plume, which is validated with the experimental observations. However, in this case a larger por-
978 tion of the material is ejected into the surrounding liquid but a rather sharp interface between the
979 ablation plume and liquid is still present, explaining the observation of non-zero reflectance ob-
980 served by PPM within the phase explosion regime (figure 12C, blue open circles).

981 At this point it should be noted that the MD simulations predict that approximately 80% of the ab-
982 lated materials is redeposited to the target surface [219]. This highlights that the alteration of the
983 ablation dynamics when moving from air to liquid and the associated redeposition results in a de-
984 creased ablation efficiency. However, up until now, the amount of redeposited material hasn't been
985 quantified experimentally. For LAA it was observed that the reflectance drops between 200 ps and
986 1 ns (see figure 12C, black full circles) within the spallation regime. This reflectance drop was in-
987 terpreted as a disintegration of the spallation layer into smaller liquid droplets, which then causes
988 complete extinction of the incident probe pulse and thus the observation of zero reflectance [158].
989 For LAL, the disintegration of the spallation layer into larger particles is expected to occur on a
990 similar timescale as deduced from MD simulations (see figure 12D and 12E). Optical probing of
991 the LAL dynamics within the time interval reveals a peculiar reflectance increase around a delay
992 time of 600 ps (see figure 12C). This rise was attributed to the disintegration of the spallation layer
993 into larger NPs, which could cause an increased reflectance due to the plasmon resonance. In fact,
994 the optical probing at 528 nm lies very close to the plasmon resonance peak of Au NPs located
995 around 530 nm for sizes larger than approximately 10 nm [252]. Thus, optical probing of the LAL
996 process allows to identify the generation of larger NPs after 600 ps. This is in accordance with
997 computational predictions, where MD simulations of Au irradiated in water show that the ejected
998 spallation layer disintegrates into larger particles on a similar timescale (see figure 12F) [242].
999 Further optical experiments have been conducted to underpin the formation of larger NPs on a sub-
1000 nanosecond timescale. For this, double-pulse laser ablation of Au in water was performed with two
1001 identical pulses that were separated by an inter-pulse delay ranging between 0 ps and 1.2 ns [243].
1002 Instead of transient reflectance, the obtained NP size distribution was monitored dependent on the
1003 inter-pulse delay time (see figure 12G). For an inter-pulse delay of 0 ps (black line) – which corre-
1004 sponds to single-pulse ablation – the particle size distribution showed a strong bimodality typical
1005 for ultrashort LAL of metal targets [253]. This bimodality may well be a result of two channels of
1006 NP generation as predicted by simulations (see figure 12H) [244]. Small primary NPs with diam-
1007 eters of several nm are generated by condensation of the metal vapor (small NPs in figure 12H),
1008 whereas large NPs with diameters of several ten nm are generated by disintegration of the ejected
1009 spallation layer due to thermodynamic instabilities (large NP in figure 12H) [43,254]. When the
1010 inter-pulse delay in the double-pulse experiments was increased, it was observed that the amount
1011 of large particles decreased gradually until a minimum amount was measured at an inter-pulse de-
1012 lay of 600 ps (see figure 12G, red line). Following this a further increase in the inter-pulse delay

1013 resulted again in a higher bimodality. The interaction of a second pulse with the ablation plume
1014 again demonstrates that a significant amount of large particles is generated within the time interval
1015 around 600 ps in accordance with time resolved probing of the reflectance signal (see figure 12C,
1016 open blue circles) and computational predictions (see figure 12F).
1017 As the efficiency of the double-pulse ablation process exhibited a minimum at an inter-pulse de-
1018 lay of 600 ps, it was speculated that a fraction of the absorbed pulse energy was used to fragment
1019 the larger 30 nm-sized particles into smaller 7 nm-sized particles, similar to LFL of laser gener-
1020 ated NPs [12]. Thus, the double-pulse experiments not only help in assessing the timescales for
1021 secondary NP formation but also represent a promising method for obtaining mono-modal NP
1022 size distributions in a single process step [243]. However, further understanding of the downsiz-
1023 ing mechanisms in double-pulse LAL is needed to fully utilize the method and obtain mono-modal
1024 NP size distributions.
1025 In conclusion, the presence of the liquid overlayer significantly alters the sub-nanosecond dynamics
1026 of LAL compared to LAA. Ranging from thermionic electron emission mediated optical break-
1027 down over confinement of liquid propagating ablated material and its redeposition to the generation
1028 of NPs. These processes determine both the process efficiency as well as the final NP size distribu-
1029 tion.

1030 **Nanosecond, microsecond and millisecond laser ablation dynamics in liquid**

1031 The sub-nanosecond LAL dynamics are mainly governed by the ablation of a liquid material layer
1032 followed by distinct NP generation channels. The dynamical processes following this are charac-
1033 terized by shockwave emission as well as CB expansion, rebound and collapse, finally leading to
1034 the generation of the NPs [158,222]. As shown in figure 13A to 13C, these dynamical processes
1035 span several orders of magnitude in time; start on a ns-, continue on a μ s- and are approximately
1036 finished on a ms-timescale [158,222,255]. The shadowgraphy images depicted in figure 13A were
1037 generated by an incoherent illumination of the ablation scene from the side. However, incoherent
1038 illumination is typically employing flashlamps as light sources, which display a limited temporal
1039 resolution in the range of several ten ns [256] to several μ s [255], thus hinder probing of nanosec-
1040 ond ablation dynamics, such as shock waves being emitted with speeds of up to 12 km/s [257] and
1041 the formation of the CB [222]. For probing these phenomena, sub-nanosecond temporal resolution
1042 is required, which typically is done with coherent laser sources, which, however, suffer from co-
1043 herent imaging artifacts, such as ringing and speckles [258]. Furthermore, high numerical aperture
1044 illumination is required for the observation of the ablation plume inside the CB [258]. Currently,
1045 there are efforts in the development of incoherent illumination sources with short pulse durations,
1046 which utilize the amplified spontaneous emission from a rhodamine dye with a temporal resolution
1047 of 100 ps [258]. However, the literature on applying these novel sources for LAL is currently ex-
1048 tremely sparse. Thus, we will focus next on the nanosecond CB and shockwave dynamics probed
1049 with coherent light sources. The preceding shockwave, which generates a low pressure region in
1050 the liquid, plays a key role in initiating this cavitation process by rapidly reducing the local pres-
1051 sure below the vaporization threshold, thereby enabling bubble nucleation and early CB expansion
1052 [259].

1053 The CB is initially generated as a flat vapor layer a few 10 ps after pulse impact due to heating of
1054 the surrounding liquid by the hot ablation front from target [244]. The generated vapor then rapidly
1055 expands, giving rise to the formation of a round CB, filled with the ablation plume containing
1056 gaseous as well as liquid species as well as evaporated solvent molecules [222]. However, optical
1057 probing of the CB on these early timescales is extremely challenging, as computational methods
1058 predict that the CB has expanded by just a couple of 100 nm at a delay time of 1 ns after pulse im-
1059 pact [244]. Nonetheless, at higher fluences and delay times of 1 ns to 2 ns the CB detaches from
1060 the ablation plume and becomes sufficiently large to be optically detected [259]. As it acts as a fo-
1061 cusing lens, it can also be readily detected in PPM experiments [158]. This result has high applica-
1062 tion relevance as it marks the time point from which subsequent laser pulses significantly interact
1063 with the emerging CB [260]. The CB generation time of about 1 ns not only determines a minimal
1064 time interval in which the ablated material may still be directly influenced by subsequent pulses,
1065 but also explains the high ablation efficiency, when employing pulse durations of about 1 ns, as
1066 the laser pulse does not experience bubble shielding on this timescale [260]. Moving on to longer
1067 timescales of several nanoseconds, the CB and shockwave expansion can be clearly detected in
1068 PPM [158,260] and PPS [195,259] experiments (see figure 13B). From these images the transient
1069 evolution of the CB radius may be extracted (see figure 13C). Modeling based on the Rayleigh-

1070 Plesset equation [257,259,261,262] may then be used to obtain quantitative data from the CB evolution, assuming spherical symmetry and incompressibility [263]. For higher accuracy, especially under strong driving pressures, compressibility can be included via the Gilmore [264] or Keller-Miksis [265] models. In cases involving non-spherical collapse or boundary effects, numerical solutions of the Navier-Stokes equation becomes necessary [266]. Regarding the conversion of absorbed laser energy into CB energy, values strongly depend on pulse duration and irradiation conditions. For nanosecond pulses, conversion efficiencies of approximately 10% have been reported [259], and values up to 33.5% at 532 nm and 53% at 1064 nm have been observed at ten times the optical breakdown threshold fluence [267]. In contrast, femtosecond-induced optical breakdown results in significantly lower conversion efficiencies, with reported values of only 0.033% of the absorbed pulse energy contributing to bubble formation [232]. Quantitative estimations not only help in understanding under which conditions the NPs grow within the CB, but also aid the understanding of the mechanism for laser fragmentation, e.g. shown for the LFL of single IrO_2 microparticles [268]. Here the quantitative analysis of the shockwave (see figure 13D, 4 ns and 20 ns) and CB (see figure 13D, 500 ns) dynamics allows the determination of the pressure inside the microparticle, which exceeds the tensile strength of the particle, highlighting a predominate photo-mechanical mechanism for the fragmentation [268].

Figure 13

Figure 13 (*previous page*): Nanosecond, microsecond and millisecond laser ablation dynamics in liquid. (A) Shadowgraphs with a tilted view depicting the microsecond ablation dynamics of a silver target immersed in water irradiated with a 7 ns, 1064 nm laser pulse with an energy of 16 mJ. The images were generated by using a cw diode laser together with a gated CCD camera. (B) Shadowgraphs depicting the nanosecond ablation dynamics of an aluminum target immersed in water after irradiation with a 5 ns, 355 nm laser with a pulse energy of 60 mJ. (C) Transient evolution of CB radius R after irradiation of a titanium sample immersed in water with a 20 ns and 1064 nm laser pulse. Probing was performed by a nanosecond Nd:YAG laser. The evolution of R is depicted for different peak fluences given in the legend in units of J/cm^2 . (D) PPM images depicted the entire laser fragmentation dynamics of single IrO_2 microparticles subjected to single 10 ps, 1040 nm laser pulses with a peak fluence of $0.18 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$. (E) Shadowgraphs depicting the interaction of a second laser pulse with the emerging CB. The second laser pulse impacts the bubble 20 μs after generation by the first laser pulse and exhibits a pulse duration of 10 ps, a wavelength of 1064 nm and a peak fluence of $3.4 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$. The target is Au immersed in water. (F) Transient development of persistent microbubbles after irradiation of an Au target immersed in water with a pulse duration of 8 ns, a wavelength of 1064 nm and fluence of $27 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$. Figure 13 A is adapted from [255], *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, vol. 489, by S. Reich et al., "Pulsed laser ablation in liquids: Impact of the bubble dynamics on particle formation", pages 106-113, Copyright (2017), with permission from Elsevier. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Fig 13 B is reprinted from [195], *Applied Surface Science*, vol. 574, by A. Chemin et al., "Investigation of the Blast Pressure Following Laser Ablation at a Solid–Fluid Interface Using Shock Waves Dynamics in Air and in Water", pages 016944332, Copyright (2017), with permission from Elsevier. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 13 C is reprinted with permission from [259] © Optical Society of America. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 13 D is adapted from [268] (© 2022 M. Spellauge et al., some rights reserved; exclusive licensee John Wiley & Sons, Inc., distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Figure 13 E is reprinted from [43] ("Two Mechanisms of Nanoparticle Generation in Picosecond Laser Ablation in Liquids: The Origin of the Bimodal Size Distribution", © 2018 C.-Y. Shin et al., published by RSC, distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License, <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>). This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0. Fig. 13 F was adapted with permission of The Royal Society of Chemistry, from [269] ("How persistent microbubbles shield nanoparticle productivity in laser synthesis of colloids – quantification of their volume, dwell dynamics, and gas composition" by M.-R. Kalus et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 19, issue 10, © 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C6CP07011F>); permission conveyed through Copyright Clearance Center, Inc. This content is not subject to CC BY 4.0.

1087 Moving on from the nanosecond to the microsecond regime, the CB further expands until reaching
 1088 its maximum radius in the range of several ten μs [270-272] to hundred μs [273,274]. Within this
 1089 regime, irradiation of the CB by a second pulse was studied (see figure 13E) [43], which indicated
 1090 that a significant portion of the incident laser pulse energy is absorbed at the interface of the CB
 1091 and the surrounding liquid, which highlights the strong shielding effect of the CB [275]. Further-
 1092 more, the generation of small satellite bubbles above the CB (see figure 13E), is associated with the

1093 second laser pulse being absorbed by NPs that are present above the CB boundary and thus con-
1094 firms the jetting of large secondary particles into the surrounding liquid as predicted by MD simu-
1095 lations [43]. Furthermore, small-angle X-ray probing experiments revealed that particle growth and
1096 agglomeration happens within the CB and NP size quenching by adding electrostatic stabilizers to
1097 the liquid are already in effect inside the CB [276].

1098 Following maximum extension, the CB starts to collapse on a timescale of hundred μs [255,270,
1099 273,274]. The collapse emits a secondary shockwave, which can transiently raise pressure and
1100 temperature in the liquid and may even trigger phase transitions [277]. After CB collapse, a large
1101 amount of NPs previously trapped inside the CB is released into the liquid [255,278]. This high-
1102 lights, that subsequent pulses at the same position can only be transmitted to the sample surface
1103 several 100 μs after the preceding pulse. For this reason, fast polygon scanners enabling scanning
1104 speeds of up to 500 m/s are employed during LAL, to spatially bypass the CB, yielding record NP
1105 productivity in the g/h range when a laser repetition rate of 10 MHz is employed [275]. Similarly,
1106 spatial beam-splitting was performed to split the pulse energy into several spatially distributed sub-
1107 beams. With several beams the available high laser pulse energy is fully leveraged at reduced repe-
1108 tition rates, while individual laser pulses bypass the CB [279].

1109 Although the ablation dynamics have reached essentially a final state several 100 μs after pulse
1110 impact, persistent microbubbles [255] may remain attached to the targets surface for several tens of
1111 ms (see figure 13F) [269]. For LAL performed in water, persistent microbubbles can shield up to
1112 25% of the incoming laser radiation [269]. This necessitates the use of flow-through LAL reactors,
1113 where generated microbubbles together with NPs are consistently removed in order to guarantee
1114 high productivity [280,281].

1115 **Conclusion and outlook**

1116 Apparently, straightforward laser processes like LAL, LFL or LML are easily executed using a
1117 pulsed laser and a beaker with the materials, but involve a cascade of subsequent energetic and
1118 structural relaxations that are difficult to disentangle. The endeavor to master and optimize these
1119 laser synthesis processes for specific applications like biophotonics, catalysis or nanoelectronics re-
1120 quires a stringent and causal identification of the structure formation steps, which is not achievable
1121 by the analysis of the final products in a batch process alone.

1122 True understanding has to take advantage of state-of-the-art diagnostics with high temporal and
1123 spatial resolution. This review has showcased that by applying structural methods like UED, time-
1124 resolved SAXS and WAXS to ultimately imaging single nano-objects by coherent imaging as well
1125 as advanced ultrafast optical imaging a wealth of observations can be made and directly compared
1126 to theory and simulation. WAXS and UED address atomic motion in complex systems allowing
1127 to disentangle excited state of irradiated NPs and their interaction with the environment, typically
1128 a fluid phase. While SAXS and CDI show shape evolution in fragmented or growing NPs even to
1129 an ultimate goal to visualize femtosecond dynamics of single objects in a single excitation cy-
1130 cle at near-atomic resolution. These methods, however, are costly and can only be realized at a few
1131 accelerator facilities around the world. Therefore, XFEL and synchrotron studies are restricted to

1132 analyzing fundamental processes, which allow transferring the knowledge to applied systems. Yet,
1133 access to these facilities is greatly facilitated by charge-free calls for experiments that are granted
1134 on pure merit basis. Optical probing is a powerful tool for the investigation of LAL dynamics as it
1135 allows to probe the entire ablation process with unprecedented temporal resolution. This not only
1136 allows to experimentally validate state of the art LAL models but furthermore paves the way to
1137 achieve record LAL productivity by identifying key limiting factors and properly addressing miti-
1138 gation strategies to overcome the limits. Based on the already impressive findings enabled by op-
1139 tical probing of the LAL dynamics, future research directions might include employing the PPI
1140 technique to LAL to directly probe the propagating ablated material front in the liquid confine-
1141 ment and follow its redeposition in the ps time range. The PPI method is especially suited for this
1142 task as it allows to probe material expansion with unprecedented resolution down to a couple of
1143 nm [198]. Furthermore, spectroscopic pump-probe techniques may present a unique opportunity to
1144 study LAL, by investigating the spectral signature in a time-resolved manner. This might allow us
1145 to precisely study NP generation pathways by spectrally monitoring the onset of NP SPR.

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